

THE FOOD ACT AS AN ELEMENT OF BIO-HARMONISTIC GLOBALIZATION

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Abstract. *The paper establishes an adequate analysis framework on the link between globalization, food consumption, health and nutrition, which can lead to a bio-harmonistic globalization. A number of issues are being addressed regarding the integrated dynamics of the power system, with emerging potential. In this sense, the bioeconomic models in food are analyzed in relation to the globalization of diversity and complementary identities, necessary to transform the world into a harmonious unit. From here and also the provision of food in relation to demographic evolution and migration, for a balanced globalization. Uncontrolled, the process will lead to a global food crisis, thus signaling a large disharmony. The study aims to find solutions related to balanced nutrition and, by applying the principles of bio economy, avoiding food waste and protecting the environment. Also, aspects of food diversity as a balancing factor from the perspective of food safety and security and the impact of health are synthesized through the mechanisms of food diversification, including at the sophisticated level of gastronomy.*

Keywords: food act, bio-harmonism, globalization, integronic, gastronomic engineering

1. Introduction

Globalization in general remains a vague, guilty theme, generally creating adversities and alarmist reactions. It is perceived as an extension (internationalization) of the market by certain people, exposed as a scarecrow, and for others it seems a natural process and, of course, a tempting intellectual fashion, stirring up emotivism and generating harsh partisanship.

Beyond these limits, it remains a serious reflection theme, either as an imminent harm, or as a source of benefits. Anyway, it is a „functional reality of post capitalism”, an implacable one, cancelling the possibility to avoid a „marching” process [3]. And, without any doubt, in this process nourishment becomes a reference element, being indispensable as „need”.

The evolution of the feeding manner and of the food typology is a known fact and accepted by all the people, but the analyses of all detail problems leads to an as correct as possible understanding and, especially, to its future dynamics within global context [1,6,7,18].

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At the same time, from the globalization perspective the world is considered as a whole with characteristics going „between *globalization* and *glocalization*, respectively between universal and particular” (NB- *Glocalization is a combination of the words "globalization" and "localization."* The term is used to describe a product or service that is developed and distributed globally but is also adjusted to accommodate the user or consumer in a local market.) Thus, the approach of cultural type emphasizes the political and economic meaning of a changing conception, but also forms of diverse participation at a more and more compressed world. This is what Roland Robertson (2000) says: „*The Globalization Concept refers to the world reduction and the growth of the awareness degree of the world as a whole*” [24].

From this perspective, we distinguish the problem regarding the development and adaptation of the food manner within globalization conditions, respectively of demographic increase in relation to the reduction of the planet resources.

Work hypothesis: we start from the idea that, consequently to globalization, sustainability of food may be achieved by *refurbishment* (as for example adaptation to the climate changes) and by increased utilization of the *food biodiversity*. In this situation, the „complexification” process inevitably leads to the system vulnerability too, implicitly to diverse disharmonies regarding food at world level, which imposes to imagine regulation and bio-harmonization mechanisms.

Within this context, the **objective** of the study is double:

- (a) to make a **diagnoses** linked to the *biodiversity of the alimentary act* (with emphasis of *technological and cultural mechanisms*, including of the *gastronomic culture* the food manner and its influence upon food systems, over time, up to the present globalization process) and
- (b) to analyze the *food globalization* by highlighting the specificity of the present phase of the feeding manner in relation to the globalization process, in the idea to find essential directions for a feasible **prognoses** of the agro-alimentary system and of the food act in its whole, regarding evolution along the decades to come.

2. Work methodology

There are used a series of study methods such as: the conceptual analyses in relation to globalization / food; managerial, technical and statistical analyses of the food act phases; or observations regarding the integronic dynamic of the alimentation system on the axes between general and particular.

3. Results and discussions

3.1. Theses and Antitheses regarding Globalization

Globalization is a phenomenon at planetary level, irrespective of our will, representing a multicausal and polyvalent process, based on „*unity in diversity*”, that is continuously fighting the unique levelling global model, given by the convergence of partisan interests generating disharmonies.

In this process, the food act must be well analyzed in the context in which there may appear vulnerabilities in food globalization. As exemplification, among frequent disharmonies there may be mentioned: - unbalanced and differential food (see *Hunger vs. Over alimentation*); - affections and falling sick because of harmful „chemicals” and of pathogen microorganisms from food and others. Consequently there is imposed the idea of *health generating food* as an important element in food globalization. This one represents an element to solve the balanced food system at planetary level, necessary to a real harmonization, process certainly also found in other fields, which leads to a bio harmonist globalization [11].

BIOHARMONIST GLOBALIZATION represents the phenomenon of transforming the world in a unity, that manifests itself at the whole globe scale, by specific means based on getting a dynamic balance sustained by the theoretic study of values and human condition in conformity with the model of the *Living Planet*, all being sustained by the moral principles applied in economic and social life, in the context of the coexistence of several different cultures integrated on the bases of the idea of ethic multiculturalism at macro level, reasonable interculturalism at micro level, based on interconnection the general framework of a **GLOCAL** management, realizing it **Emergent interlocking (NEXUS)**.

(NB: Emergence = interaction of components of a system, having as finality the emergence of the new of a superior order)

3.2. Globalization, Man and the Alimentary act

Food must be regarded from the point of view of the human being under three aspects: (a) food as nourishment; (b) food as a stimulus of the emotive tonus; (c) food as spiritual element, to which man confers symbolic significations.

Of principle, at planetary level, man can NOT be satisfied with a food mixture, as reasonably as he may be prepared, food meaning more than the quantity and need to survive, which imposes the *food act to mean an integration of psycho-social elements sustained by technical and biological aspects and of production ones*.

The food act and the bio harmonist globalization refer to assuring food in relation to demographic evolution and migration (which also is a principle in the bio harmonization process). Therefore, based on the concept of the *Georgescu-*

Roegen concept, certain opinions [22] show that the number of population that may live on Earth is directly proportional with the terrestrial reserves of material and energetic resources (S) and inversely proportional with the speed of their consumption (r) and with the considered period (t), which may be expressed by the formula:

$$n = S/(r \times t).$$

A not at all negligible script describes a menacing disharmony, namely: the potentiality of a world food crises. Thus, the propagation of the food crises from a state becomes a global problem of mankind because the effects of this crises may be in dynamics of avalanche, spreading within the whole regional system and then, possibly, at world level.

For example, in case a state will NOT anymore be able to feed its population, all those having relationship with the respective state would be affected. More than this, all the countries from the region could be affected by the crisis increasing the risk of regional affairs. In order to solve the crisis, if the resources of that state were insufficient, it would implicitly be necessary other states assistance (especially developed countries) and the one of international institutions.

In case major cataclysms do not appear, the globe population would faster increase, towards approximately 9 billion at the midcentury, and experts [1, 10, 18, 23, 25] consider that only **doubling** the present food production until 2030 would bring salvation!

The UNO system [27]: The World Food Program (WFP) yearly gets to more than 80 thousand of persons by the food help offered in 75 countries (approximately 11,500 persons work for the organization, out of which a large part are situated in remote zones, in order to directly help poor persons).

The plan draws 4 WFP major objectives: (1). To save lives and protect living means in emergency situations; (2). To sustain food and nourishment security, as well as to rebuild living means in fragile settlements or during post-conflict periods; (3). To reduce the risk and help people, communities and countries to respond food and nourishment needs; (4). To reduce malnourishment and break famine cycle.

We consider that it is very useful to apply the bio economic model to the food act too, idea that imposes analyses concerning the biological and technical relation between food and natural environment, as well as modalities to economically sustain food globalization by capitalizing biodiversity and diversifying food.

3.3. Food diversification - sustaining mechanism of Bio-Harmonist Globalization

It is known that biodiversity is a complex network of life that sustains us all. All our food reserve and sustainable development in this field [26] is based on biodiversity (as for example: coral reefs and seaweed „produce” fish we feed with; birds and insects pollinate our crops, and, of course, crops have plants as an origin, and animals exist due to plants etc.).

A simple analyses shows us that there is an OVERCONCENTRATION on a limited number of „star” plants (4 species: wheat, rice, maize, potatoes), well known ones and others are neglected, that might become very valuable ones (approximately 100-150 species of plants furnish the great majority of the world food, and other some thousands have capitalization potential). Also about this theme, the DIVERSIFICATION of the capitalization of animal breeding species is imposed (there are about 10-15 species frequently today such as livestock in farms), for economic utilization, technically and sanitary-veterinary controlled hundreds of species from the terrestrial (ex. hunting) and aquatic fauna.

Without entering into advanced technical and biological details, we consider it useful to highlight a series of SOLUTIONS for *bioharmonist globalization*.

Fig. 1. Integration mechanisms in the globalization of alimentation

Those on bioeconomic models from the food production systems would be more important, the integroneic alimentation model (i.e. the systems of food production, by successive and complementary integrations / the *integroneic* dynamics). Thus there may be pursued biotransformation in the trophic chain of food ecosystems, in relation to the organism integrated metabolism (Fig.1).

The bioharmonization mechanism also has in view biotransformation. We refer for example to QUALITATIVE *energetic transformations* in food processing [2, 9, 17, 19]. It is taken into account that, based on knowing the correct composition and association, to get to a better digestion, absorption, *biodisponibility* and, finally, to a *biotransformation* at organismic level, as well as to a better ECO-BIODISPONIBILITY and/or ECO-BIOTRANSFORMATION at ecosystem level (see the below cachet).

Specification	Description
ECO-BIODISPONIBILITY	– Fraction from total food quantity and the corresponding ergo-nutritional compounds that get to the metabolic circuit of an integrated organism in the trophic chain of a given ecosystem.
ECO-BIOTRANSFORMATION	- The totality of chemical transformations that food suffers during the processing cycles, modifications of ecologic, biologic and physical-chemical properties that influence productivity and efficiency at every trophic level.

We find these mechanisms, under different forms, in the flow of the alimentary act which in food processing is supposed to sustain successive eco-bio-transformations within the sustainable agriculture running in bioeconomic animal husbandry able to provide organic raw materials for food processing and producing local products in the territory and finally leading to culinary production as shown in the schema presented in Fig.2 [2, 9, 10, 14, 15, 16, 21].

Biodiversity protection does not only mean to save species and habitats. It means to assure the access to water and food and help thus ourselves face the severe effects of climate changes at global level, that already affect our capacity to produce food.

Biodiversity is essential in food security at global level, but based on the equilibrium of the situation at local level (Table 1).

MECHANISMS OF FOOD DIVERSIFICATION
(INTEGRONIC DYNAMICS OF FOOD BIO TRANSFORMATIONS = energo-nutritive transformations in relation with food successive processings)

Fig. 2. Food integrated and controlled diversification in the flow of the alimentary act

Table 1. Solutions for future balance and development in the World Alimentary System

No.	Strategic direction
1	Application of the bioeconomic model in the alimentary act.
2	Food diversification and superior capitalization of genetic resources that belong to a large scale of biodiversity.
3	Adaptation at the conditions of global and regional reality at present.
4	Harmonization of the alimentary system by local resource capitalization.
5	Minimization of food waste.
6	World spread of gastronomic culture for the good knowledge of diversity and increase of understanding between people.

There may be observed that the alimentary act presupposes an integration of psycho-social elements sustained by technical-biological and production aspects, all being necessary for the application of the *bioharmonic principles* in structuring the world alimentary system [8]. There is aimed decentralized, identity and complementary harmonized globalization (based on the wealth of local products), as it is described in the synthesis of Table 2.

Table 2. Agro-food contribution of local communities in a bioharmonist globalization

<i>N o.</i>	<i>Contribution</i>	<i>Specification</i>
1	Stimulation of local economy	- Money spent at local farms and producers remain in the local economy, thus generating economic improvement, but also more jobs at other local enterprises.
2	Less displacement	- Locally produced food has to cover a much shorter way until market, which means that it is consumed much less fuel and it generates less gas with greenhouse effect.
3	Less waste	- Due to shorter distribution chains in the local product distribution, depositing and trade process, the quantity of waste food diminishes.
4	More freshness	- Local food is fresher, healthier and tastier, because it gets quicker from the farm to the consumer's dish, thus less nutritive substances being lost and food doesn't alter so fast.
5	Beneficial for the soil	- Food local production encourages local agriculture diversification, which reduces the dependence on monoculture – i.e. to cultivate a single type of culture on a large area, to the prejudice of the soil.
6	Attracting tourists	- Local food promotes agro tourism and farmers 'markets, as well as opportunities to visit local farms and producers, which helps to attract tourists to the zone.
7	More connected communities	- Local increase of food production contributes to create and maintain more vivid communities, by connecting consumers with farmers and producers that furnish locally produced healthy food.

Perspective alimentary harmonization in globalization is linked to the fact that man can't be satisfied with a food mixture, as reasonably as it may be prepared [9, 14, 20, 24]. This fact because alimentation means much more than the need to survive, situation in which understanding and the pleasure of the alimentary act are to be found in *the gastronomic culture*. Gastronomy gets special valences, especially in the globalization process, adapted to specific conditions from totally different geographic zones.

Another element with the potential to avoid a food crisis and to harmonize the food act in general, refers to food waste, especially with regard to food waste from public food establishments (eg restaurants). In the world, between a quarter and a third of the food consumed is wasted (!) and this loss can be precisely the difference between a proper diet and malnutrition in many countries around the world, according to a report of World Bank. The food crisis in a state is a global problem of mankind because the effects of this crisis are spreading throughout the regional system and then, possibly, worldwide.

The gastronomic culture in globalization represents the following elements: - human knowledge and multiculturalism; - recognition of specific values / originality of alimentation; - new food manners; - unique experiences/tourism gastronomy etc.

An overview of the historical evolution of the main characteristics of food polivalence and complexity starting from the 17th century till the beginning of the 21st century is synthetically presented in the cassettes given below [4,5,12,13].

The end of the 20th century and nowadays, we are facing the appearance of new trends such as: gastronomy/molecular cuisine, culinary constructivism, abstract cuisine, and the future could offer kitchen robotics, biocellular food, synthetic food and others.

INFLUENCE OF GLOBALIZATION UPON MANKING GASTRONOMIC CULTURE

No.	RECENT HISTORIC PERIOD	CHARACTERISTICS REGARDING ALIMENTATION POLIVALENCE AND COMPLEXITY	
		MAJOR EVENT	GASTRONOMIC SPECIFICITY
1	17th and 18th century period	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - spices and geographic discoveries - The French revolution 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> □ Complicated food based on flavours and taste: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - with awareness of organoleptic elements and especially the control of culinary preparations taste with the first apparition of the sophisticated French cuisine, with diverse typologies: - bourgeois cuisine / complrx cuisine - working class' cuisine (bistros / at home)
	19th century period	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - unprecedented scientific development: especially of chemistry and physics; rational / principal / and metabolic feeding 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> □ Apparition of food chemistry – („gastro-chemistry” revolution) : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - what has fundamented <i>Haute Cuisine</i> and with its distinct style of <i>Classic Cuisine (Cuisine Classique)</i>
2	20th century period	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - conceptual evolution of gastronomy in the first half of the 20th century and of trends from contemporary cuisine 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> □ End of historic cuisine and, with the apparition of New Cuisine („La Nouvelle Cuisine”) new gastronomic models appear: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fusion - Fast food - Excellence cuisine and others.
	End of 20th century period. – beginning of the 21st one	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - gastronomy based on physico-chemical, biological, genetic, ecologic, etc. Integronic and scientific bases, with feeding on the balance principle (harmonyof health generating, hedonic and integronic type). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> □ Apparition of new trends: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - gastronomy / molecular cuisine, - culinary constructivism, - abstract cuisine (<i>element by element or „note à note”</i>), all these also being based on frontier sciences in biology and nutrition (nutrigenomics, metabolomics, transcriptonics and others.)
NB:In perspective it is imagined: kitchen robotics, biocellular food, synthetic food and others.			

4. Conclusions

(1). Bioharmonist globalization proposes a viable model regarding spiky controversies from today’s world concerning globalization, by imagining the structure in which there is functionally made a *NEXUS*, i.e. a commune zone of

osmosis between ethnic multiculturalism at the human society level („macro”), formal interculturalism at the level of citizens and groups („micro”) and economic and social balanced globalization, reference model applicable in life fundamental element: *food*, i.e. on direction of alimentary act.

(2). Bioharmonist globalization is based on an alimentation adapted to present reality (ex.: climate changes whatnot) which imposes food diversification and biodiversity capitalization, based on openness, innovation and continuous change, so that the benefits of the extent of globalization may non-discriminatorily reflect upon all those it has included.

(3). By bioeconomic approach and by the model of integronic alimentation (*consequently to successive and complementary integrations*) there may be highlighted biotransformation in the trophic chain of alimentary ecosystems, in relation to the organism metabolism, i.e. of certain mechanisms of bioharmonization (*such as eco-biodisponibility and eco-biotransformation too*).

(4). The present demographic rhythm at planetary level imposes as important priority to double food production until the year 2030, in order to reduce subnutrition and break the famine cycle.

(5). In bioharmonist globalization a first solid step is linked to the avoidance of food waste, which represents a regulating solution that aims health, by the difference between an adequate diets and overeating registered in certain countries on the globe.

(6). The spread of gastronomic culture on the world, for the good knowledge of diversity and improvement of communication between people will lead to efficiency increase and health generating impact of the alimentary act, with benefic results for a realistic prognoses regarding evolution of the alimentary system in its whole in the next decades (integration regarding agro-zootechnical production, products of the food industry, processing and obtaining culinary preparations).

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TOTAL PHENOLIC CONTENT AND ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY OF SOME AROMATIC HERBS USED IN TRADITIONAL ROMANIAN CUISINE

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Abstract. *Lovage (Levisticum officinale), parsley (Petroselinum crispum), tarragon (Artemisia dracunculus) and thyme (Satureja hortensis) extracts were obtained in 60% ethanol. Total phenolic content (TPC) was determined using the Folin-Ciocalteu phenol reagent method. Antioxidant activities of the extracts were evaluated by 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH•) free radical-scavenging ability and ferric-reducing antioxidant power (FRAP) assay. The hydroalcoholic extract obtained from Satureja hortensis had the highest total phenolic content and the highest antioxidant activity. A significant and positive high Pearson's correlation between TPC and DPPH• assay and between TPC and FRAP assay respectively was observed for all plant extracts. The results indicated that phenolic compounds were the main contributor to antioxidant activity in the investigated aromatic herb extracts).*

Keywords: aromatic herbs, total phenolic content, antioxidant activity

1. Introduction

Aromatic herbs used in Romanian cuisine are herbaceous (leafy) plants that add flavour and colour to all types of meals. Aromatic herbs represent an important source of biologically active compounds, such as phytochemicals and phytoalexins, recognized for their beneficial health effects, and thus have also been used in folk medicine. Both phytochemicals and phytoalexins are made of simple phenolics and polyphenolics, which are known as bioactive compounds responsible for the antioxidant activity in plants, besides some vitamins (A, C and E) [2]. Phenolics are compounds that contain at least one hydroxyl group (-OH) attached to an aromatic ring. Phenolic compounds are ubiquitous components of plants and herbs that act as reactive oxygen species (ROS)/reactive nitrogen

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species (RNS) scavengers and also, some have antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antiallergic, antimutagenic, antiviral antithrombotic, and vasodilatory activities. More than 8,000 phenolic compounds as naturally occurring substances from plants have been reported [15]. Half of these phenolic compounds are flavonoids presenting as aglycone, glycosides and methylated derivatives [1].

The most used plants in traditional Romanian cuisine are thyme (*Satureja hortensis*), parsley (*Petroselinum crispum*), lovage (*Levisticum officinale*) and tarragon (*Artemisia dracunculus*). They are used in Romanian cuisine as seasoning due to their strong flavour. These plants have a distinctive taste and impart unique tastes and flavours of salads, cooked food, meat, and fish. The leaves are gathered before flowering and the flowering shoots can be used fresh or dried.

The objective of this study was the determination of total phenolic content (TPC) in a selected plant, as well as the evaluation of the antioxidant capacity of their hydroethanolic extract.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Plant Materials and Reagent

The plants were collected from the region of Ilfov County, in June. The fresh aromatic herbal was transferred in polyethylene bags to the laboratory on the same day. They were rinsed with de-ionized water, dried-plotted, weighed and dried to a constant weight in an air-forced oven maintained at 25 °C. Dried samples were grounded and stored until analysis in brown air-tight bottles.

All chemicals were from Fluka Chemicals, Sigma-Aldrich and Merck.

2.2. Extraction procedure

The extraction method used for dried samples has as follows: 40 mL of 60% aqueous ethanol was added to 0.5 g of dried sample. Then 10 mL of 6 M HCl was added. The extraction mixture was then sonicated for 15 min and refluxed in a water bath at 90 °C for 2 hrs. The mixture was then filtered and made up to 100 mL with ethanol.

2.3. Determination of total phenolics content (TPC)

The total phenolic contents (TPC) were determined spectrophotometrically according to the Folin-Ciocalteu colorimetric method [4]. Briefly, 20 µL extract was mixed with 1.16 mL of distilled water and 100 µL of Folin-Ciocalteu reagent, followed by the addition of 300 µL of Na₂CO₃ solution (20%). After 30 min of incubation at 40 °C, the absorbance of the reaction mixture was

measured at 760 nm. Results were expressed as mg of gallic acid/g dry weight sample (mg GAE/g DW).

2.4. Antioxidant activity

2.4.1. 1, 1-Diphenyl-2-Picrylhydrazyl radical (DPPH[•]) scavenging activity

Experiments were carried out according to the method of Blois, modified by Proestos and Varzakas [13]. Briefly, a 1 mmol/L solution of DPPH radical solution in methanol was prepared and then, 1 mL of this solution was mixed with 3 mL of extract. After 30 min, the absorbance was read at 517 nm. Butylated hydroxytoluene (BHT) was used as positive controls. The percentage inhibition of the DPPH radical by the samples was calculated using the following equation:

$$\% \text{ DPPH radical - scavenging} = \frac{\text{Abs control} - \text{Abs sample}}{\text{Abs control}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

2.4.2. Ferric-reducing antioxidant power (FRAP) assay

The FRAP reagent was prepared by mixing 38 mM sodium acetate in distilled water pH 3.6, 20 mM FeCl₃•6H₂O in distilled water and 10 mM 2,4,6-tri(2-pyridyl)-s-triazine (TPTZ) in 40 mM HCl (10:1:1, v/v/v). The samples (50 µl) were incubated with FRAP reagent (4 mL) at 37 °C for 40 min in the dark. The absorbance of the resulting solution was measured at 593 nm. Trolox (6-hydroxy-2,5,7,8-tetramethylchroman-2-carboxylic acid) was used as a reference antioxidant standard. FRAP values were expressed as g Trolox/100 g dry weight plant (g Trolox/100 g DW) [14].

2.5. Statistical Analysis

Excel (Microsoft Co, Redmond, WA, USA) and SPSS (version 19.0 statistical software, SPSS Inc., Chicago, USA) packages were used for statistical analysis. Results represented means ± s.d. of six determinations. Pearson's coefficient was used to evaluate the correlations between TPC and antioxidant activity.

3. Results and discussions

Aromatic herbs have long been reported as a prospective hub of natural antioxidant compounds, particularly plant secondary metabolites, such as, phenolic compounds which are generated by the plant to defend itself or to promote the growth under unfavourable conditions. The phenolic compounds have attracted the attention of researchers due to their attractive biological properties,

such as their antioxidant activity. But, the content in polyphenols and their antioxidant activity differ from one plant to another and also depend on the climatic factors, but also the harvesting period.

The total phenolic contents of investigated aromatic plants are presented in Fig. 1. The highest level of total phenolics was found in leaves of thyme (*Satureja hortensis*), followed by leaves of tarragon (*Artemisia dracunculus*). Parsley (*Petroselinum crispum*) and Lovage (*Levisticum officinale*) had TPC low levels. Our results agree with the literature, which reports similar TPC.

Fig. 1. Total phenolic content in the aromatic herbs

Thus, for *Thymus vulgaris*, the values reported for TPC were between 4.67 and 5.90 g GAE/100 g DW, according to the harvesting period [17]. In the leaves of *Artemisia dracunculus*, dried at room temperature and darkness [7], reported TPC of 58 mg GAE/g DW. TPC levels in parsley and lovage leaves, frozen at -20°C until analysis, were 360.89 and 577.04 mg GAE/g FW [10]. The total phenolic content level depends on the drying methods. TPC levels in *Thymus vulgaris* were between 1,400 and 3,920 mg/100g DW, the highest level being reported for oven drying at 50°C with microwave pre-treatment.

Phenolic compounds act as antioxidants by various mechanisms such as donation of H atoms, donation of electrons or chelation of transitional metal ions. This study investigated the antioxidant activity of four aromatic herbs by two methods, DPPH \cdot scavenging activity, and FRAP antioxidant power. However, these

methods have different reaction mechanisms and do not necessarily measure the same activity [12]. DPPH• assay is based on hydrogen transfer, whereas the FRAP assay is based on electron transfer reactions.

Fig. 2. DPPH radical scavenging activities of aromatic herbs extracts

The DPPH radical scavenging ability of aromatic herbs extracts is given in Fig. 2. The capacity of extracts to act as H atom donors ranged between 82.02% and 28.50%. The highest DPPH• scavenging activity was recorded for thyme extract, followed by tarragon, lovage, and parsley, following the same ranking order as for total phenolics content. In this experiment, there was a positive correlation between total phenolic content and the percentage of DPPH radical scavenging.

The FRAP assay is based on the ability of phenolic compounds to reduce Fe^{3+} to Fe^{2+} . When the reduction of Fe^{3+} to Fe^{2+} occurs in the presence of 2,4,6-tripyridyl-s-triazine, the reaction is accompanied by the formation of a coloured complex with Fe^{2+} (absorption at 593 nm). The reducing power appears to be related to the degree of hydroxylation and the extent of conjugation in phenolics. FRAP values in the aromatic herbs examined ranging from 1.22 ± 0.66 g Trolox/100g DW in parsley to 8.52 ± 0.97 g Trolox/100g DW in thyme (Fig. 3). For tarragon FRAP values were close to those obtained for thyme (6.81 ± 0.92 g Trolox/100g DW), whereas, those obtained for lovage were close to those obtained for parsley (1.98 ± 0.59 g Trolox/100g DW).

Fig. 3. Antioxidant activity of aromatic herbs extracts expressed as ferric-reducing antioxidant power (FRAP)

It is established a significant correlation between DPPH \cdot scavenging and TPC content $R^2 = 0.9546$, $p < 0.05$, whereas the correlation between FRAP and TPC is $R^2 = 0.9196$. A significant correlation is between DPPH \cdot scavenging and FRAP ($R^2 = 0.9743$, $p < 0.05$).

The correlation between total phenolic contents and antioxidant activity has been widely studied in different foodstuffs such as fruit and vegetables [6, 8, 18]. Antioxidant activity of fruits and vegetables significantly increases with the presence of a high concentration of total phenolic content [5, 16]. For this reason, many researchers reported a positive correlation between phenolic content and the antioxidant activity [3, 9, 11].

Conclusions

- (1). Lovage (*Levisticum officinale*), parsley (*Petroselinum crispum*), tarragon (*Artemisia dracunculus*) and thyme (*Satureja hortensis*) leaves contains important levels of phenolic compounds.
- (2). Thyme and tarragon leaves have the highest content of phenolic compounds.
- (3). The phenolic compounds from the investigated aromatic herbs used in Romanian cuisine have antioxidant properties acting as an electron and hydrogen donors.

- (4). Thyme and tarragon leave hydroethanolic extracts have the highest antioxidant activity.
- (5). Between the antioxidant activity and the total phenolic content, there is a significant positive correlation.

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RESEARCHES REGARDING THE SUPERIOR VALORISATION OF BY-PRODUCTS FROM THE WINERY INDUSTRY, AND THE OBTAINING OF BAKERY PRODUCTS WITH FUNCTIONAL PROPERTIES

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Abstract. *The paper presents in summary the great potential of the wine industry in Romania, as a supplier of by-products with special biochemical characteristics. From all of the by-products known, the most notable are the epicarp and grape seeds, which can be used directly in the bakery industry, and due to the high content of fiber, antioxidants and unsaturated fatty acids, represent a high functional potential. The undertaken studies aimed to introduce in the technological flow an optimal quantity of grape seed powder (GSP), respectively grape epicarp powder (GEP), in order to maximize the functional effect, and the sensory characteristics. For this purpose, the nutritional and rheological profile of mixtures of wheat flour and semi-degreased grape seeds and grape epicarp were first realized. Subsequently, the bakery products with additions of grape epicarp in a proportion of 5, 10, 12, 15% and respectively semi-degreased grape seeds in proportion of 3, 5, 7, 9% were made on an industrial technological flow. The obtained bakery products were analyzed from physical and sensorial point of view, the conclusions showing that the maximum percentage of by-products use is 12% for grape epicarp, and 7% for semi-degreased grape seeds respectively.*

Keywords: functional bakery products, grape seeds and epicarp

1. Introduction

1.1. The concept of functional food product

In the current socio-economic context, human nutrition leads to chronic imbalances characteristic of modern man, which is why healthy eating will become in the near future an important therapeutic means for maintaining or even regaining health. Nutritional improvements for a healthy diet have the effect of reducing the health costs that are today extremely expensive for chronic diseases caused mainly by unhealthy eating and sedentary lifestyle [10].

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With the growing population and food security needs, either the re-formulation of existing food products or the development of new foods will be targeted.

Research in this area covers a wide range of topics, such as: the need for primary prevention of chronic diseases caused by non-sanogenic diets; development of nutritional intervention programs; innovation in the field of functional ingredients and bioactive compounds with high potential; new methods for encapsulating valuable bioactive compounds; design and development of innovative products; personalized nutrition; various aspects of food safety and quality.[1], [9], [11-14]

Therefore, the creation of a food with a nutritional profile as complete as possible, to meet the specific requirements of the consumer (related to age, health, type of daily activities), is a constant goal of current research in nutrition. In Europe, functional food enjoys a special interest, the topic being addressed by the 47 projects funded on this topic, in which 513 institutions participated in the FP5, FP6, FP7 competitions with 150 million euros [15].

Within this work, the potential of new bakery products developing by adding in wheat flour by-products from the winery industry with high content of bioactive compounds, such as grape seeds and grape epicarp.

1.2. The concept of functional food product

In the case of Romania, the annual consumption of bread per capita is about 90 kg, compared to the European average of 50 kg and 93% of Romanians consume bread daily (Ministry of Health, 2011). These data demonstrate the importance of bread in the Romanian diet. A recent study found that 83% of consumers prefer white bread, followed by black bread (25%) and homemade bread (23%) [8].

In her work, Apostol L., [1], has studied the increase in the nutritional value of bakery products using two different sources of nutrients, namely Jerusalem artichoke (*Helianthus tuberosus L*) and hemp seeds (*Cannabis sativa L*) partially degreased, a waste resulting from the technological process of obtaining cold-pressed oil. The experimental results on the chemical composition of Jerusalem artichoke tubers revealed that, of the total constituent substances, about 63% is the inulin content. The inulin-rich content of this ingredient used in experimental research confirms that Jerusalem artichoke tubers have functional potential. Also, the mineral content is high, namely : potassium, calcium and magnesium.

Hemp seed flour has in its composition, in appreciable quantities, substances with high functional potential, such as fibers, minerals and last but not least essential fatty acids, with an optimal ratio of ω -6 / ω -3 of 3: 1 [1].

From the point of view of the functional potential of both *Jerusalem artichoke* and partially defatted hemp seeds, the experimental results revealed that the terms "rich in fiber", a source of calcium, potassium, magnesium and zinc can be issued, providing more than 15% of the recommended daily dose per 100 g of product. All these indications may be preceded by the term "naturally".

Fortified wheat flour with different percentages of Jerusalem artichoke (5%, 10%, 15% and 20%) and partially defatted hemp (5%, 10%, 15% and 20%) and a mixture of the two ingredients (5% Jerusalem artichoke + 6%, 10% and 15% partially defatted hemp seeds) was analyzed from a compositional point of view and the influence of these ingredients on the nutritional composition and rheological properties of wheat flour was studied [1].

The conclusions of the study show that the sample of bread with the addition of 5% Jerusalem artichoke and 6% partially defatted hemp seeds has the highest coefficient of acceptability of the participants in the sensory analysis [1].

In the doctoral thesis (Popa A., 2013) has developed a new, functional food product with the potential to be widely consumed daily, as is the case with white bread reformulated by adding oat derivatives (oatmeal and oat bran) as functional ingredients. The raw materials studied for their use in the development of new bakery products, with functional potential, were: *Solomon* oats and its derivatives, sifted oatmeal and oat bran, as well as mixtures of wheat-oat flour (flour content or oat bran in proportions of 20, 40, 60, 80 and 100%), and all experimental results were compared with white wheat flour 550 [10].

In order to establish the technology of obtaining breads with the addition of oats, as a functional ingredient, baking tests were performed, as well as comparative physico-chemical and sensory analyzes.

Research has led to the optimization of mixtures of wheat flour and oat derivatives to obtain bakery products with nutritional mentions of: "iron source", "magnesium source", "magnesium rich" and "zinc source" with a positive sensory impact from the consumer.

In its article, Bhattarai S, [2], carried out a study on improving the functional properties of bakery products, by adding buckwheat flour and green tea. Products with the addition of buckwheat flour in proportions of 20%, 30%, 40% and 50% and 1%, 3% and 5% green tea were made, which were compared with a control sample of wheat flour. The products were assessed sensorial based on 5 parameters: core color, shell color, taste, smell and overall appearance. The optimal variant identified by the test team was the one with content of 40% buckwheat and 3% green tea. In this variant, the lipid content was $2.93 \pm 0.31\%$, similar to rye bread specialties, in which the value of this parameter is approx. 2.6%.

The fiber content was $2.12 \pm 0.16\%$, similar to that of rye bread containing approx. 2.36% fiber. The protein content was $16.56 \pm 1.12\%$, significantly higher than that of wheat flour products, due to the appreciable intake of protein from buckwheat flour [2].

The humidity of the optimized product was 27.17%, significantly lower than the average humidity of wheat flour products with the value of approx. 33.8% (Bhattarai S, et al., 2012), given that the sensory testing team did not specify significant differences in texture in the analyzed products. As the lipid content in the product developed ($2.93 \pm 0.31\%$) was higher than in the control sample (1.9%), the effects of satiety and persistence of taste were more intense. The protein content was 16.56%, significantly higher than the normal protein content of white flour bread (6-10%) [2].

The authors found that the shelf life of the product increased by approx. 3 days, compared to white flour bread kept in similar conditions, a phenomenon attributed to the antifungal activity of catechin EGCG in green tea [2].

Other ingredients used to make functional bakery products are: extracts of *Pleurotus Ostreatus* (1-3)(1-6) β -Glucan (Frioui M. et al., 2017), mangosteen fruit flour *Garcinia Mangostana* (Ibrahim U.K., et al., 2018), chia seeds flour (Kurek M.A., 2019), etc. [3], [4], [5], [6], [7].

2. Materials and research methodology

2.1. Materials

Grape epicarp flour used in the experimental research was a by-product obtained during manufacture of red *Vitis vinifera* from Romania, and was furnished by a local wine-making factory. Grape skins were collected after the grapes were crushed and the juice was obtained. Fresh samples were manually sieved to separate skin fraction from the seeds. Skin fractions were dried and grounded. The level of degradation of the components of this material may be considered low because all the steps were performed at low temperature.

The grape seed flour used in the experimental research was supplied by the Romanian company SC 2E PROD SRL, Alexandria, Teleorman. After the mechanical extraction of grape oil, the partially degreased seeds were dried and crushed.

The first wheat flour used in the study was 480 type (ash, d.m. – 0.48%) and was provided by Titan S.A. (Bucharest, Romania). Four types of mixtures of 480 type wheat flour and different proportions of defatted grape seeds flour were obtained, in the following ratios: 97:3, 95:5, 93:7 and 91:9 (w/w).

The second wheat flour used in the study was 550 type (ash, d.m. – 0.55%) and was provided by M.P. Băneasa-Moară S.A. Bucuresti. Three types of mixtures of 550 type wheat flour and different proportions of grape epicarp flour were obtained, in the following ratios: 95:5, 90:10, 88:12 and 85:15 (w/w).

2.2. Research methodology

Physico-chemical indicators of the samples were determined using the following methods:

- Method of determining humidity (SR ISO 712:2009);
- Method of determining acidity (SR 90:2007);
- Method of determining the total ash content (SR ISO 2171:2009);
- Method of determining the total fat content, Soxhlet (SR 90:2007);
- Method of determining the crude protein content (SR ISO 20483:2007);
- Method of determining the crude fiber content AOAC 991.43;
- Method of determining the fatty acid content by gas chromatography;
- Method of determining the mineral content.

The rheological characteristics of the doughs obtained were determined using the Mixolab apparatus, the Chopin + protocol. It uses the standardized protocol ICC No. 173 for a complete characterization of the rheological behavior of the flour (protein network, starch and enzymatic activity) and produces a simple graph of interpretation of the results. The device measures in real time the torque (expressed in Nm) produced by the passage of the dough between the two mixing arms, and studies rheological and enzymatic parameters. The operating parameters of the device for the analysis of the rheological behavior of the dough are the following: tank temperature 30°C, mixing speed 80 min⁻¹, heating speed 2°C / min, the total time of an analysis being 45 minutes. C1, C2, C3, C4, C5 are specific points on the rheological diagram, and TC1, TC2, TC3, TC4, TC5 are their correspondent time (min). C1 it is used to determine water absorption; C2 measures protein weakening as a function of mechanical work and temperature; C3 measures starch gelatinization; C4 measures hot gel stability; C5 measures starch retro-gradation in the cooling phase.

3. Results and discussions

3.1. Mixtures of wheat flour and grape seeds flour

The results obtained for mixtures of wheat flour and grape seed flour (97:3, 95:5, 93:7 and 91:9) are presented in table 1 (protein, ash, total fat and crude fiber) and table 2 (mineral content).

Table 1. Components of wheat flour and its mixtures with grape seed flour

	Samples				
	P0 (100:0)	P1 (97:3)	P2 (95:5)	P3 (93:7)	P4 (91:9)
Protein	10.50 ± 0.10	10.63 ± 0.15	10.72 ± 0.13	10.81 ± 0.19	10.9 ± 0.14
Ash	0.48 ± 0.01	0.56 ± 0.03	0.61 ± 0.04	0.66 ± 0.04	0.71 ± 0.02
Total fat	0.90 ± 0.05	1.05 ± 0.05	1.15 ± 0.05	1.25 ± 0.03	1.35 ± 0.05
Crude fiber	0.69 ± 0.10	3.6 ± 0.18	7.3 ± 0.28	10.1 ± 0.34	14.3 ± 0.86

Table 2. Mineral content of wheat flour and of its mixtures with grape seed flour

Sample	Mineral content (mg mineral/100 g sample)				
	Ca	Mg	K	Cu	Fe
P0 (100:0)	43.8 ± 0.59	47.7 ± 0.55	187 ± 0.75	0.78 ± 0.09	1.1 ± 0.22
P1 (97:3)	54.66 ± 0.40	58.20 ± 0.33	192.20 ± 0.93	1.49 ± 0.09	1.29 ± 0.21
P2 (95:5)	61.90 ± 0.10	65.21 ± 0.56	195.66 ± 0.34	1.68 ± 0.11	1.58 ± 0.22
P3 (93:7)	69.15 ± 0.74	72.21 ± 0.68	199.13 ± 1.10	2.34 ± 0.20	1.84 ± 0.37
P4 (91:9)	74.32 ± 0.13	79.02 ± 0.63	207.12 ± 1.13	2.97 ± 0.13	2.02 ± 0.54

It can be observed that the flour mixes has a high content of Ca, Mg, Cu and Fe, and fibers.

Table 3. Rheological behavior of mixture of grape seed flour and wheat flour

Parameter	Abbreviation	P0 (100:0)	P1 (97:3)	P2 (95:5)	P3 (93:7)	P4 (91:9)
Water absorption (%)	CH	58.2	58.0	56.7	56.9	57,0
Stability (min)	ST	8.50	9.10	8.88	9.48	9,83
Amplitude (Nm)	A	0.100	0.104	0.081	0.078	0,105
Maximum consistency during:						
– phase 1 (Nm)	C1	1.143	1,065	1,111	1,081	1,068
	TC1	1.20	1.22	1.12	1.35	1,05
– phase 2 (Nm)	C2	0.461	0.469	0.486	0.428	0,416
	TC2	16.62	16.68	16.40	16.63	17,00
– phase 3 (Nm)	C3	2.041	2.030	2.106	2.129	2,091
	TC3	24.53	24.43	24.08	23.17	23,62
– phase 4 (Nm)	C4	1.553	1.479	1.458	1.360	1,429
	TC4	30.95	30.67	29.95	30.63	28,75
– phase 5 (Nm)	C5	3.131	2.977	3.009	3.033	3,032
	TC5	45.02	42.00	45.02	45.02	45,02

Fig. 1. Mixolab curves for grape seed and wheat flour and their mixtures

In table 3 are presented the main rheological parameters acquired by Mixolab equipment. A significant different behavior can be observed during enzymatic retro-gradation for the probes P2, P3, P4.

3.2. Mixtures of wheat flour and grape epicarp flour

The results obtained for the case of mixtures of wheat flour and epicarp flour (95: 5, 90:10, 88:12, and 85:15) are presented in table 4 (protein, ash, total fat and crude fiber) and table 5 (mineral content).

Table 4. Components of wheat flour and its mixtures with grape epicarp flour

Composition % d.m.	Samples				
	P0 (100:0)	P5 (95:5)	P6 (90:10)	P7 (88:12)	P8 (85:15)
Protein	13.2 ± 0.24	13.3 ± 0.25	13.40 ± 0.25	13,47 ± 0.23	13.50 ± 0.21
Ash	0.55 ± 0.01	0.85 ± 0.02	1.25 ± 0.02	1.39 ± 0.01	1.63 ± 0.03
Total Fat	1.04 ± 0.07	1.25 ± 0.06	1.49 ± 0.07	1.58 ± 0.04	1.71±0.07
Crude Fiber	1.9 ± 0.12	2.49 ± 0.35	3.05 ± 0.38	3.34 ± 0.44	3.63 ± 0.56

In table 6 are presented the main rheological parameters acquired by Mixolab equipment.

Table 5. Mineral content of wheat flour and of its mixtures with grape seed flour

Sample	Mineral content (mg mineral/100 g sample)				
	Ca	Mg	K	Cu	Fe
P0 (100:0)	44.9 ± 0.61	48.7 ± 0.53	189 ± 0.76	0.87 ± 0.19	1.6 ± 0.24
P5 (95:5)	66.5 ± 0.63	50.0 ± 0.55	301.8 ± 0.87	1.38 ± 0.10	1.67 ± 0.25
6 (90:10)	89.1 ± 0.79	52.2 ± 0.57	416.1 ± 0.99	1.97 ± 0.19	2.21 ± 0.28
P7 (88:12)	103.4 ± 0.66	53.1 ± 0.52	478.2 ± 0.89	2.08 ± 0.20	2.46 ± 0.27
P8 (85:15)	111.3 ± 0.89	54.5 ± 0.59	531.2 ± 1.01	2.54 ± 0.22	2.76 ± 0.30

Table 6. Influence of grape epicarp flour added to wheat flour in different proportions on mixolab characteristics (rheological behavior)

Parameter	Abbreviation	P0 (100:0)	P5 (95:5)	P6 (90:10)	P7 (88:12)	P78 (85:15)
Water absorption (%)	CH	56.0	56.5	57.2	57.6	57.8
Stability (min)	ST	10.07	10.28	10.73	11.14	12.23
Amplitude (Nm)	A	0.103	0.093	0.095	0.109	0.117
Maximum consistency during:						
– phase 1 (Nm)	C1	1.10	1,111	1,099	1,098	1,097
	TC1	5.55	6.37	8.68	9.77	10.45
– phase 2 (Nm)	C2	0.454	0.469	0.486	0.528	0.667
	TC2	16.95	16.68	17.28	17.65	17.72
– phase 3 (Nm)	C3	2.327	2.432	2.491	2.487	2.490
	TC3	24.53	24.43	24.08	23.08	23.17
– phase 4 (Nm)	C4	2.216	2.258	2.296	2.269	2.275
	TC4	27.58	26.78	26.37	26.14	26.01
– phase 5 (Nm)	C5	3.664	3.607	3.221	3.106	3.008
	TC5	45.02	45.02	45.2	45.2	45.02

Fig. 2. Mixolab curves for grapes epicarp flour and wheat flour mixtures

From figure 2 can be observed that the samples with 12% and 15% of grape epicarp are characterized by a final consistency significant reduced.

3.3. Discussions

Following the analysis of the results of the experimental researches, a series of assessments are made regarding the increase of the nutritional value with the increase of the content of added by-products, respectively the rheological behavior of the doughs formed with the obtained flour mixtures [5-7].

It was thus found that the addition of grape seed flour or grape epicarp slightly increases the value of the protein content in the mixture. At the same time, the amount of fiber in the mixture increases by over 225% in the case of the addition of grape seed flour (7% addition), and by about 90% in the case of the addition of grape epicarp (15% addition).

The calcium content increases by 57%, and the magnesium content by 51% in the case of the addition of grape seed flour (7% addition).

In the case of the addition of grape epicarp flour (15% addition), the calcium content increases by 154%, and the potassium content by 184%.

The rheological studies performed show a slight reduction (by about 10%) of the viscosity of the dough in the dough formation phase and a similar increase of the stability period. The gelling phase of starch provides higher viscosities with the increase of epicarp and grape seed addition.

The addition of grape seed flour produces a sudden decrease in the torque resistant immediately after the maximum point reached in the gelatinization phase of starch, which indicates a rapid hydrolysis of it. The sample with 15% of grape epicarp is characterized by a final consistency of the products reduced by 20%, which excludes it as a potential variant for the formation of bakery products.

Analyzing the limits imposed by the dough processing technology, it is observed that the maximum limits for the additions studied are 7% grape seed flour, respectively 12% grape epicarp flour.

Conclusions

(1) Fortification of bakery products by adding food by-products is a large research topic, with favorable results, on the one hand on increasing their nutritional value and on the other hand contributes to the implementation of the concept of circular economy by superior capitalization of bio-resources in Romania [9], [5-8].

(2) The research carried out in the paper highlights the potential of increasing the content of fibers and minerals through the addition of grape seed flour and grape epicarp flour, as well as the limits imposed by the rheological conditions necessary for the formation and technological processing of the dough [6], [10].

(3) Thus, the results of the physico-chemical and rheological analyzes performed present as possible the variants of additions of 7% grape seed flour, respectively 12% grape epicarp flour.

(4) Future research directions envisage the addition of various additives (gluten, enzymes) in order to improve the baking properties of flour mixtures with high degrees of replacement with by-products from the winemaking industry, respectively grape seeds and epicarp [7].

(5) An important aspect of enriching the nutritional value of food products is the choice of vector foods, of those foods consumed by the entire population, homogeneous and stable, which can be processed and obtained under standardized conditions [1], [3], [7], [10].

(6) Functional food innovation is not a linear, single-actor process, but the result of a collective effort by a variety of actors such as food companies, universities, intermediate research institutes, authorities, consumers and support infrastructure, including investors and consulting firms. Cooperation between

food producers will become increasingly important, for example in the distribution of research risks and costs.

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RESEARCHES AND CONTRIBUTIONS TO PLANT SORGHUM CROP IN THE CONDITIONS OF CLIMATE CHANGES

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Abstract. Dobrogea is the most drought area of Romania (average 1961-2016 :464 mm rainfall precipitation). Climate change in recent years has accentuated this phenomenon .For farmers from this area sorghum crop is a solution. At Sport Agra in Amzacea, in the last few years there have been experimented new sorghum crop technologies designed to face the current climate changes. These technologies include the following elements: changing the planting epoch with one month before the usual period recommended by classical technologies; (beginning of April in order to benefit from the soil's humidity la 4-5 cm depth boosting the germination process); choosing early hybrids in order to avoid the drought season which starts in June; applying adequate crop protection treatments, with pre-emergent and post-emergent herbicides and last generation insecticides. The agricultural crops in this area are not irrigated, so the authors proposed a new technology, planting the crops earlier. In this way the plants will benefit from the moisture of the soil accumulated in the winter. The obtained production from sorghum crop was over 10t/ha for most of the hybrids tested.

Keywords: Sorghum, climate changes, technologies

1. Introduction

The history of sorghum it is written that it has been appeared in the 9th century in Zanzibar. From Asia it has been transported by a brush American citizen Franklin. In the 13th century, it was cultivated in Italy (Filipescu, 1943) [5]. At the level of 1943, Italian sorghum was produced in Romania for export.

At the level of 1986 there were cultivated 90,000 ha with an average production of 1,860 kg ha (Statistical Yearbook 1990) [12]. At the level of 2003, in Romania there were cultivated 11,092 ha in 8,765 farms (Muntean et al, 2008) [9].

Sorghum is a plant with rooted fascicle that grows in the soil reaching up to 1.25 meters, thus ensuring the water needed during the vegetation period (drought tolerance).

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2. Crop Technology

The crop taking into study is sorghum, which is recommended for these arid areas; called "the camel of crops" due to its drought resistance (Ayana and Bekele, 2004)[1], sorghum requires the following technological elements: Selecting early hybrids to overcome the drought periods that occur between the 5-10th of June until the 20-25th of August(Manole D., 2018)[8]. There are recommended hybrids with shorter vegetation period (Poschiscanu et al.,2015) [11].

Sorghum planting is recommended between 20th April and 10th May (Trotus et al. 2015) [13] ensuring a minimum of 120-140 kg/ha of Nitrogen (Owen, 1967) [10], treatment of seeds before planting with chemicals containing thiamethoxam, (Manole D., 2018)[7] pre-emergence herbicide with Dual Gold (metalacolor) 1.5 l/ha and post-emergence with Buctril Universal 0.8 l/ha (bromoxinil+2.4D).

The results from comparative crops in a 4-year dynamics have demonstrated sorghum crops with outstanding yields of over 10 t/ha.

The agricultural crops in this area are not irrigated, so the authors proposed a new technology, planting the crop earlier by about a month. This way the plants will benefit from the moisture of the soil accumulated in the winter time, and passing the dry period starting from June to July.

Table 1. Experience of Sorghum in Constanta County 1961-Research Station "Valu lui Traian"

Hybrid	Plant height cm	Vegetation period days	Yields Kg/ha	+ -
NK 210	117	144	8,413	3,359
NK 300	156	143	8,152	3,098
NK 120	118	128	7,905	2,851
X 3000	109	125	7,646	2,592
X 3021	129	135	7,611	2,557
X 3057	170	130	7,476	2,422
X 3007	108	148	7,322	2,268
NK 310	113	146	7,057	2,003
NK 230	103	136	6,867	1,854
NK 145	225	130	6,815	1,761
NK 135	122	131	6,670	1,616
NK 135 11	136	145	6,657	1,603
X 3037	102	145	6,459	1,405
NK 140	118	138	5,741	687
HD 302 (corn)	220	132	5,054	-

Note: As shown in Table 1 all 14 hybrids of sorghum at the level of 1961 have surpassed the hybrid HD 302 of corn between 687 – 3,359 Kg/Ha in the Research Station "Valu lui Traian".

3. Chemical composition of Corn and Sorghum

Table 2. Chemical composition of Corn and Sorghum

Specification	Protein	Grease	Cellulose	Ash
Corn	9.3-14.7	4.5-5.3	1.9-2.6	1.3-1.7
Sorghum	9.6	3.4	2.2	1.5

Sorghum absorbs from the atmosphere 50-55 to/ha carbon dioxide from deciduous forests 16 to/ha.

Sorghum contains 20-40 kg carbohydrate juice per 100 kg/strains which can result in cheaper fuel (Budescu, 2004) [3].

Very important for sorghum crop it is its contain in essential amino acids and tryptophan which will provide the advantage to feed cattle, pigs and especially chicken (Brouk. M.J. Bean B, 2005)[2].

4. The arable land in Constanta county and the main crops, 2017 – 2019

Table 3. The arable land in Constanta county and the main crops 2017 – 2019

Crop	2017		2018		2019	
	ha	Kg / ha	ha	Kg / ha	ha	Kg / ha
484103 ---- 483671						
Wheat	186,855	4,682	172,122	5,652	194,375	5,084
Barley	28,410	5,116	47,182	6,702	43,200	5,213
Corn	41,032	6,906	49,185	8,475	56,710	5,282
Sunflower	118,635	2,927	95,123	3,512	115,310	2,505

Even if the corn it's a much more profitable then the other crops, because the land is not irrigated, the area cultivated with corn it is not very large: 41,032 ha – 2017 – 56,710 ha – 2019. At the level of the year 2019 wheat and barley were cultivated on an area of 237,575 ha, meaning about 50% of the arable land of Constanta County.

Experimental plots were placed at S.C. Sport Agro S.R.L. Amzacea, Constanta County. The experience was situated on a land belonging to the South Dobroudja plateau, represented by a cambic chernoziom, with a profile deeper than other chernozioms, a blackish-brown soil of 40-50 cm thickness, medium texture (Demeter, 2009) [4]. The content of nutrients was: mobile P index - 72; N index - 4; Humus - 3.11; K index - 200; Neutral pH - 7.2. The climate is deeply temperate continental, with an average annual temperature of 10.7-12.12°C, with a high temperature between June and August. Meteorological data are presented in

Tables 4, 5 and 6 from Research Station "Valu lui Traian", Constanta, starting from 2016 to 2018 in comparison with the average between 1961 – 1990.

5. Precipitation regime

Table 4. Precipitation and temperature during 2016 growing vegetation season (Valu lui Traian Station, Constanta County)

	Month								
	Jan.	Feb.	March	April	May	June	July	Aug.	
Periods	The growing season 2016: Precipitations (mm) for 10-day periods								Sum
1-10	0	12.0	10.0	0	60.0	3.5	56.0	4.0	145.5
11-20	95.0	18.5	19.0	0	21.01	20.0	0	0	173.5
21-30	15.0	0	15.0	20.0	16.0	0	0	0	66.0
Sum	110.0	30.5	44.0	20.0	97.0	23.5	56.0	4.0	385.0
	Average 1961-1990: monthly values of precipitations (mm)								Sum
	27.7	24.0	29.1	31.8	37.7	47.1	38.9	37.4	273.7
	The growing season 2016: Mean air temperature (°C) for 10-day periods								Mean
	2.5	4.1	6.8	10.3	13.9	19.8	22.6	23.2	12.9
11-20	4.8	5.2	7.9	12.9	16.8	21.4	24.2	22.6	14.57
21-30	4.3	5.4	10.2	13.5	18.7	22.1	23.8	21.4	14.92
Mean	3.9	4.9	8.3	12.2	16.5	21.1	23.5	22.4	14.1
	Average 1961-1990 monthly values of mean air temperature (°C)								Mean
	0.4	0.9	4.4	9.7	15.3	19.4	21.9	16.9	12.12

Table 5. Precipitation during 2017 growing vegetation season (Valu lui Traian Station, Constanta County)

	Month								
	Jan.	Feb.	March	April	May	June	July	Aug.	
Periods	The growing season 2017: Precipitations (mm) for 10-day periods								Sum
1-10	60.0	5.0	4.0	0	13.0	18.0	9.0	0	109.0
11-20	10.0	13.5	31.0	35.0	12.0	6.0	0	0	107.5
21-30	0	2.0	5.0	6.0	2.0	4.0	92.0	6.0	117.0
Sum	70.0	20.5	40.0	41.0	27.0	28.0	101.0	6.0	333.5
	Average 1961-1990 monthly values of precipitations (mm)								Sum
	27.7	24.0	29.1	31.8	37.7	47.1	38.9	37.4	273.7

Table 6. Precipitation during 2018 growing season of sorghum(Valu lui Traian Station, Constanta, Romania)

	Month								
	Jan.	Feb.	March	Apr	May	June	July	Aug.	
Days	The growing season 2018: Precipitation (mm)								Sum
1-10	0	9	6	2	64	35	98	0	214
11-20	44	31	37	0	28	0	2	0	142
21-31	19	80	26	0	0	41	47	0	213
Sum	63	120	69	2	92	76	147	0	569
	Average 1961-1990 monthly values of precipitations (mm)								Sum
	27.7	24.0	29.1	31.8	37.7	47.1	38.9	37.4	273.7

5.1. Average rainfall - Research Center Amazacea 2010 – 2019

Table 7. Average rainfall – Research center Amazacea 2010 – 2019

Year	Monthly precipitations (mm)												Total year
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII	
2010	82.5	74	90	19	56	54	297	0	25	47	16	38	801.5
2011	50.8	25	34	40	54	18.5	96	11	11	78	1	56	475.3
2012	126	34	25	32.5	94	4.5	61	37	10	35	15	81	555
2013	42	17.5	22	25.5	60.5	75.5	85	20	65	76.5	13	20	522.5
2014	113	2	40.5	42	61.5	228.5	30	89	43	151	40	106	946.5
2015	83	40	74.5	48	0	25.5	35	41	17	93	40	3	500
2016	110	30.5	55	20	97	23.5	56	4	23	72	47	3	541
2017	70	20	40	41	27	29	111	6	5	55.5	65	50	519.5
2018	63	120	68	2	92	76	147	0	3	3	57.5	47	678.5
2019	36	8	16	35.5	18	14	44	7	37	44	9.5	27.5	178.5
Average	77.63	37.1	46.5	30.55	56	54.9	96.2	21.5	24.8	76	29.6	44.6	615.53 9 year 595,38 10 year
178.5 mm precipitations between January the first – August 31 2019													

As written in Table 4, the year 2016 provided a higher amount of rainfalls between May and June, 111.3 mm higher than the multiannual average. These precipitations favored the development of sorghum crops. In the Tabel 5 the precipitations in May, June were 55 mm. – 29.8 mm. in comparison with the multiannual average of 84.8 mm., but in July it was happened 101.0 mm. The same

it was happened at SC Sport Agra- Amzacea. As shown in Tabel 6, the year 2018 was very rich in precipitations in Research Station Valu lui Traian, May and June registered 168.0 mm and July 147.0 mm. The same rainfall level was in Amzacea as shown in Table 7. Looking at the four years of research, the year 2019 was the dryest year in a total growing season of sorghum, reaching 178.5 mm. Tabel 7 in comparasion with multianual precipitations starting since 2010 the year 2019 was reach only 296,5 mm. total year, wich means a difference of 319,03 mm. and an average of total ten years it was 615,53mm., so a total diference of - 319,03mm..

Regarding the sorghum crop, the main technological links pursued by the research team consisted of the following: Choosing early hybrids to overcome the burning periods that occur between June 5 till August 20-25, Recommending shorter vegetation hybrids, Providing a minimum amount of 120-140 kg/ha of nitrogen, Treatment of seeds before planting with chemicals containing thiamethoxam to combat *tanymecus sp.* in the early stages of vegetation, Pre-emergence herbicide with Dual Gold (metalaclor) 1.5 l/ha and post-emergence with Buctril Universal 0.8 l/ha (bromoxinil+2.4D).

Photo 1. Research field of Sorghum at SC Sport Agra S.R.L. before harvesting 2019 (Original)

Photo 2. Researches field of Sorghum 2017, SC Sport Agra S.R.L. before harvesting (Original)

6. Demonstrative plots for Sorghum - Amzacea 2016

Table 8. Demonstrative plots for Sorghum - Amzacea 2016

Hybrid	Pre-emergent plant	Surface sqm	Seeds/ha	Sowing date	Emergence date	Yields kg/ha	Harvest time
ES Arfrio	Wheat	2,195	230,000	9 April	18 April	10,013	02.sep
ES Aqulion	Wheat	2,195	230,000	9 April	18 April	12,340	02.sep
ES Alize	Wheat	2,195	230,000	9 April	18 April	11,785	02.sep
Arack	Wheat	2,195	230,000	9 April	18 April	11,919	02.sep
Arkanciel	Wheat	2,195	230,000	9 April	18 April	10,022	02.sep
Arkanciel	Wheat	2,195	230,000	2 May	14 May	7,810	18.sep
ES Foehn	Wheat	2,195	230,000	9 April	18 April	8,601	02.sep

The experiments were carried out in 2016 on 6 hybrids, as shown in Table 8. Most of the hybrids were planted one month earlier (9 April) (Manole D., 2018)[6] compared to the classic technology recommended by specialists (Trotus et al. 2015) [13] and EURALIS. Hybrid Arkanciel was planted and recommended (May 14).

Table 8 shows the data regarding sorghum productivity consisting in very high yields of about 10-11 tons / ha for most hybrids, due to the change of the planting date as the plants to benefit from the moisture accumulated in the soil during the winter and also to avoid the drought crashes beginning in June (Manole D., 2018)

[8]. It can be seen that the Arkanciel hybrid registered a production increase of 2,212 kg/ha, obtained by its earlier planting and also 16 days earlier harvested.

Table 9. Demonstrative plots for Sorghum - Amzacea 2017

Hybrid	Pre-emergent plant	Surface sqm	Seeds/ha	Sowing date	Emergence date	Yields kg/ha	Harvest time
Alize	Wheat	2,195	220,000	4 April	14 April	10,439	24.aug
Foehn	Wheat	2,195	220,000	4 April	14 April	11,504	24.aug
Arkanciel	Wheat	2,195	220,000	4 April	14 April	10,336	24.aug
Arkanciel	Wheat	2,195	220,000	4 May	16 May	6,900	5.sep
Albanus	Wheat	2,195	220,000	4 April	14 April	10,130	24.aug
Typhon	Wheat	2,195	220,000	4 April	14 April	8,859	24.aug
Armorik	Wheat	2,195	220,000	4 April	14 April	10,645	24.aug

The data obtained in the experimental year 2017 are presented in Table 9. The planting took place this year on April 4, and the same hybrid Arkanciel was planted 2 times, first on April 4 and secondly on May 4. From the presented data, it can be seen that this year, due to the earlier planting, led to high production increases of over 10,000 kg / ha. This year, the Arkanciel hybrid recorded an increase of 3,436 kg/ha and Arkanciel was planted on April 4 and harvested 13 days in advance. Table 9 presents the data on the technical sheet of sorghum culture on the two plots. The experiments in the plot 1 were made on 2,195 sqm. The treatment of the seed prior to planting was performed with chemicals containing thiamethoxam (Manole D.,2018) [7]. Pre-emergence herbicide was carried out with Dual Gold (metalacrol) 1.5 l/ha and post-emergence with Buctril Universal 0.8 l/ha (bromoxinil+2.4D).

Table 10. Demonstrative plots for Sorghum - Amzacea 2018

Hybrid	Pre-emergent plant	Surface sqm	Seeds/ha	Sowing date	Emergence date	Yields kg/ha	Harvest time
Albanus	Wheat	2,195	240,000	11 April	24 April	10,100	22. Aug
Foehn	Wheat	2,195	240,000	11 April	25 April	11,000	22. Aug
Arkanciel	Wheat	2,195	240,000	11 April	25 April	10,669	22.Aug
Arkanciel	Wheat	2,195	240,000	20 April	28 April	8,634	09. Sep

The results in the year 2018 are presented in Table 10. As can it can be seen, thanks to the same technologies applied, the Arkanciel hybrid planted on April 11th achieved a production by 2,035 kg / ha higher than the same hybrid planted on April 20th and 18 days harvested before Arkanciel planted on April 20.

Table 11. Demonstrative plots for Sorghum - Amzacea 2019

Hybrid	Pre-emergent plant	Fertilizer	Surface sqm.	Number seeds	Planting	Emergency	Flowering	Level kg/ha	Harvesting	Moisture %	MHL	
<i>Foehn</i>	Wheat	Granoro	300 kg	560	250,000	26.03.2019	15.04.2019	01/07/19	6,907	21.08.2019	15.9%	79.6
<i>Alize</i>	Wheat	Granoro	300 kg	560	250,000	26.03.2019	15.04.2019	01/07/19	6,844	21.08.2019	13.8%	77.2
<i>Alize 2</i>	Wheat	Granoro	300 kg	560	250,000	15.04.2019	1.05.2019	01/07/19	5,513	21.08.2019	14.8%	79
<i>Albanus</i>	Wheat	Granoro	300 kg	560	250,000	26.03.2019	15.04.2019	01/07/19	5,323	21.08.2019	14.1%	76
<i>Shamal</i>	Wheat	Granoro	300 kg	560	250,000	26.03.2019	15.04.2019	01/07/19	7,034	21.08.2019	14.6%	76.9
<i>Anggy</i>	Wheat	Granoro	300 kg	560	250,000	26.03.2019	15.04.2019	01/07/19	6,273	21.08.2019	16.3%	75.8

In Table 11, there are the research data of the year 2019, the driest year since the weather observations are made in Romania for the Dobrogea region. The research team has changed the hybrid Arkanciel and planted Alize hybrid to see what it will happen with another genetic potential. Alize hybrid planted on March 26 achieved an average production of 6,844 kg / ha and the same hybrid planted on April 15 of the same year achieved an average production of 5,513 kg / ha, meaning a surplus difference of 1,331 kg / ha and a difference of 1% extra humidity for the Alize hybrid planted on April 15th.

Photo 3. Ph.D. Eng. Dumitru Manole 2019 – before starting Sorghum harvesting (Original)

7. Economical Data, SC Sport Agra SRL Amzacea, Constanta County, 2017 – 2019

All the researches have to be applied for the farmers' benefit following the data presented in the Tables 12 and 13. Sorghum crop is much more profitable than other crops grown in Constanta County such are: wheat, soybean, corn. From our

market information, sorghum crop has to be promoted looking at the climate changes especially in Dobrogea Region.

Table 12. Economical Data SC Sport Agra SRL Amzacea, Constanta County, 2017

Specification	Corn	Soybean	Sunflower	Sorghum	Wheat
Mechanical works	316	318	329	269	377
Seeds	125	204	149	101	92
Fertilizer	165	74	130	156	188
Pesticides	183	124	156	51	137
TOTAL Cost/Ha	789	720	764	577	797
kg/ha	8,364	1,992	3,800	8,859-11,504	7,271
Price / ton	130	299	294	130	164.7
Gross income	1,087	595	1,117	1,151-1,495	1,197
Leu/Euro – 4.65 Lei	+298	- 125	+353	+574-918	+400

Table 13. Economical Data SC Sport Agra SRL Amzacea, Constanta County, 2019

Specification	Corn	Soybean	Sunflower	Sorghum	Wheat
Mechanical works	239	214	192	201	500
Seeds	96	64	82	83	111
Fertilizer	266	98	232	133	112
Pesticides	148	71	150	57	111
TOTAL Cost/Ha	698	447	656	474	834
kg/ha	7,050	1,433	3,431	7,034	6,690
Price / ton	142	277	279	142	162
Gross income	1,001	397	957	999	1,083
Leu/Euro – 4.77 Lei	+303	-50	+301	+525	+249

Conclusions

(1). At Sport Agra Amzacea, there have been experimented in the last few years new and improved sorghum crop technologies in order to adapt to the new climate changes. These technologies comprise the technological elements mentioned below:

(2). Selecting early hybrids to overcome the drought periods that occur between the 5-10th of June until the 20-25th of August. There are recommended hybrids with shorter vegetation period.

(3). Changing the planting period - the hybrids were planted one month earlier (26 March - April 4 and 9).

(4). The results from comparative crops in a 3-year dynamics have demonstrated sorghum crops with outstanding yields of over 10 t/ha.

(5). The agricultural crops in this area are not irrigated, but those data of research demonstrated that the new technologies of planting sorghum one month earlier were much better, even in 2019. In this way the sorghum crop will benefit of much more moisture accumulated into the soil in winter time and will avoid the attack of *Tanymecus sp.* The year 2019 was a very dry year.

(6). During the vegetation period, the amount of precipitations (April, May, June) was 58 mm. The hybrid Alize planted on March 23, 2019 recorded 6,844 kg / ha and the same hybrid planted on April 15, 2019 recorded 5,513 kg / ha, so the difference was 1,331 kg / ha and the difference of grains moisture was 1%.

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LEVELS AND TRENDS IN INTERNATIONAL AGRO-FOOD TRADE OF ROMANIA IN THE 2011-2018 PERIOD

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Abstract. *The paper highlights the foreign trade situation of Romania focused on agricultural products. At national level, for 2011/2018, the annual variational aspect of export / import is reproduced, by the value levels of the annual balances. From the dynamic analysis of the external trade balance, for the agri-food products can be delimited periods reflecting: a negative level with reference to the period 2011-2013 (the values being between -425 and -751 million €); a positive level for 2013 and 2014 (values between 332 and 456 million €) and a negative level for the period 2016-2018 (values between -137 and -1134 million €). The average for the whole period remains negative (-€ 412 million). The analysis of the balance in the structure of the main groups of agri-food products signifies a differentiation of the respective annual values: positive levels for plant products, negative annual values for live animals and animal products, along with food, beverages and tobacco. For the group of animal or vegetable fats and oils, the positive values of the balance are ascertained. In conclusion, from the analysis of the balance of agri-food products, the question arises of a concern from which the profitability of the export as a whole or with reference to the live animal products and animal products arises.*

Keywords: export, import, trade balance, average, annual rate

1. Introduction

The presented paper highlights the commercial situation of foreign trade of Romania focused on agri-food products. At national level, in the structure of the period 2011/2018, the annual variational aspect of export / import is presented, for which the value levels of the annual balances are analyzed, with differences being noted. Effectively the dynamics analyzed by expressing value and percentage-comparative of the balance for the agri-food products in the system of the external trade in the analyzed dynamics can be delimited periods that reflect positive and negative levels. Synthetically, it is intended to present the variational annual rhythm levels for the main groups of agri-food products, according to which the export / import trends can be known.

2. Working methodology

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Suitable for highlighting the level and exchanges of foreign trade in agri-food products, the methodology used was appropriate to surprise this problem. The database constituted the export / import activities and the balance of foreign trade by analyzing in the staggered structure of four main groups of agri-food products (e.g. vegetables, livestock and animal products, food, beverages and tobacco, p. animal or vegetable fats and oils). The name and structural classification of these agri-food products was taken according to the delimitations mentioned in the specialized literature [1] [5] [6].

In the annual dynamics of the period 2011-2018 the analysis was based on the indicators that were presented in absolute and percentage values. The percentages achieved annually in the agri-food sector were presented by comparisons both with respect to the total national level and by forms of the structure of the groups of agri-food products with respect to the base year 2011 and the average of the represented period.

The determination of the annual growth rates surprised the existence of the oscillations of the indicators that was due to a permanent change due to the levels of exports / imports (the differentiation between the level of export / import indicators at certain times for the dynamics of the period 2011-2018). So how many times is the level of export / import from the end of the period compared to the one from the beginning of the analyzed period [2] [3] [6].

2.1 . The overall exchange of agri-food products

In all the historical stages of Romania, the issue of foreign trade with agri-food products had an importance that was permanently taken into consideration. The paper refers to the elements of export / import / balance by absolute values but also by percentage-comparative forms. With reference to the period 2011-2018, the data presented in Table 1 reflect the structure of the overall level of the external agri-food trade.

The export analysis shows annual variational levels of growth, with reference both to the total and to the agri-food products. Effectively compared to the annual average as well as the annual growth rate, by comparing the level of trade with agri-food products with the total country, there are variational levels that register a decreasing tendency.

The import expressed through the annual values rendered records lower levels, which in the succession of the years are played through increases. At the same time, they express for the import of agri-food products, an annual average of € 5902 million and an annual rate of 1.08% (noting that this level of the rate is lower than the total country).

The situation of the balance structure expresses for the agri-food products negative situations for all the years of the period analyzed both on the whole country and on the whole of these agri-food products.

Table 1. Structure of the overall level of the external agri-food trade compared to the total foreign trade in Romania, for the period 2011-2018

	Export			Import			Balance		
	Total country	Agri-food	% from the total	Total country	agriculture	% from the total	Total country	Agri-food	% from the total
	mil €	mil €	%	mil €	mil €	%	mil €	mil €	%
2011	45,292	4,021	8.88	54,952	4,446	8.09	-9,660	-425	4.4
2012	45,069	4,044	8.97	54,703	4,795	8.77	-9,634	-751	7.79
2013	49,562	5,284	10.66	55,317	4,952	8.95	-5,755	332	-5.78
2014	52,466	5,577	10.63	58,522	5,121	8.75	-6,056	456	-7.53
2015	54,610	5,918	10.84	62,971	6,055	9.62	-8,361	-137	1.64
2016	57,392	6,169	10.75	67,364	6,789	10.08	-9,972	-620	6.22
2017	62,644	6,407	10.23	75,604	7,423	9.82	-12,960	-1,017	7.84
2018	67,723	6,501	9.6	82,840	7,635	9.22	-15,116	-1,134	7.5
Average	54,345	5,490	10	64,034	5,902	9	-9,689	-412	4.25
Annual rhythm	1.06	1.07	1.01	1.06	1.08	1.02	x	x	x

Source: N.I.S., 2019, Exports (FOB) by counties and by sections / chapters of the Combined Nomenclature (NC), <http://statistici.insse.ro:8077/tempo-online/>, Accessed on Feb.15, 2020 [4]

Fig. 1. The evolution of total foreign trade in Romania (Million Euro)

Figure 1 shows graphically the export / import levels in the dynamics of the analyzed years.

From the analyzed set results import values that exceed both the level of export of the national economy and for the export of agri-food products. At the same time, it can be mentioned that the annual rhythms register levels close to both export and import.

2.2 . The structure of the exchanges of agri-food products for export / import from Romania

It is an aspect to be analyzed for the main product groups which is the subject of foreign trade activities. This is because the groups of agri-food products register different levels and comparative forms in the dynamics of the years. For this the whole of the export of agri-food products is presented under the quantitative aspect (percent versus total rendered against the annual value levels), next to the qualitative aspect (aspect reproduced by a comparison in the dynamics of the analyzed period, but expressed as a percentage for each of these groups of products).

a) The structural level of the agricultural products involved in foreign trade in Romania. It seeks to know at national level, the levels of product groups as a percentage of export / import contribution (Table 2).

Table 2. The structure of the agri-food products of the foreign trade in Romania, for the period 2011-2018

Year	Export					Import				
	Total export agri-food products mil €	From which %				Total import agri-food products mil €	From which %			
		Vegetal products	Animal s and anima products	food, beverage s and tobacco	animal or vegetabl e fats and oils		Vegetal product s	Animal s and anima product s	food, beverage s and tobacco	animal or vegeta ble fats and oils
2011	4,021	52.15	14.52	27.33	6.01	4446	29.77	21.70	42.98	5.51
2012	4,044	48.71	18.07	28.68	4.52	4795	29.53	21.58	43.89	4.98
2013	5,284	56.49	14.09	24.88	4.54	4952	29.38	22.49	43.96	4.13
2014	5,577	55.08	13.32	27.77	3.81	5121	29.56	23.94	43.31	3.20
2015	5,918	51.96	13.21	31.05	3.785	6055	33.64	20.71	42.60	3.03
2016	6,169	55.71	13.19	27.94	3.14	6789	34.30	21.22	41.68	2.78
2017	6,407	54.65	14.76	27.26	3.29	7423	32.26	22.75	42.39	2.58
2018	6,501	55.23	13.76	27.54	3.44	7635	30.34	23.23	44.16	2.25
Average	5,490	54.02	14.20	27.83	3.93	5902	31.31	22.22	43.08	3.37

Source: N.I.S., 2019, Exports (FOB) by counties and by sections / chapters of the Combined Nomenclature (NC), <http://statistici.insse.ro:8077/tempo-online/>, Accessed on Feb.15, 2020 [4].

The total export recorded in the analyzed dynamics registers an increase, which is found only in the case of the group of vegetable products to which a majority

comparative level can be added (between 48.71% and 56.49% against the total export). Similarly, significant levels can be considered the group of food, beverages and tobacco (which dynamically recorded percentage levels against the total between 24.88% and 31.05%), the group of live animals and animal products (comparative weights record values between 13, 19% and 18.07%), and finally the group of fats and oils can be listed (the weights being between 3.14% and 6.01%).

The import for the same product groups is represented by comparative levels, compared to the food, food and beverages and tobacco (between 41.68% and 43.96% comparative weights), followed by the vegetable products (the weights comparison being between 29.38% and 34.30%), live animals and animal products (with weights between 21.22% and 23.94%), followed by the group of fats and oils with the lowest levels (at this the group being noticed the succession of a decrease in the dynamics of the years, which varies between 42.98 / 43.96% and 41.68%).

Fig. 2 shows the evolution of the export / import of agri-food products, showing the annual variations.

Fig. 2. Evolution of the import and export of agri-food products for the period 2011-2018 (Million Euro)

Synthetically, on this side of the analysis, it is emphasized that for the period analyzed, the share of exports is a priority over imports only to vegetable products and fats. For imports, there is a priority in the group of food, beverages and tobacco, along with the group of live animals and animal products.

b) Foreign trade in plant products from Romania. It represents the most important sector of the Romanian agricultural trade, with special reference to the share held. The analysis of the data presented in Table 3 shows through the comparative forms shown with respect to 2011 as well as to the average of the aspects considered edificatory regarding the foreign trade with plant products:

-the export of vegetable products records in the annual dynamics analyzed successive growths, the annual rate being 1.08. By comparing with the base year 2011, it shows differentiated levels, with a maximum growth of 171.24% in 2018 being highlighted.

- the import for the group of plant products is maintained in a successive growth, so that the annual rate is similar to the export. Looking at the comparison with 2011, there are exceedances of these levels in the successive years (the oscillations being between +6.94% and +75.90%). Considering as a basis of comparison the average of the period can be found below the average levels (> 100%) for the period 2011-2014 and levels above the average (< 100%) for the period 2015-2018.

Table 3. Foreign trade in plant products from Romania, for the period 2011-2018

Year	Export			Import			Balance		
	Total mil €	% compared to:		mil €	% compared to:		mil €	% compared to:	
		2011	average		2011	average		2011	average
2011	2,097	100	70.70	1,324	100	71.64	773	100	69.14
2012	1,970	93.94	66.41	1,416	106.94	76.62	554	71.66	49.55
2013	2,985	142.34	100.64	1,455	109.89	78.73	1,529	197.80	136.76
2014	3,072	146.4	103.57	1,514	114.35	81.92	1,558	201.55	139.35
2015	3,075	146.63	103.67	2,037	153.85	110.22	1,037	134.15	92.75
2016	3,437	163.90	115.88	2,329	175.90	126.02	1,108	143.33	99.10
2017	3,502	167.00	118.07	2,395	180.89	129.59	1,107	143.20	99.01
2018	3,591	171.24	121.07	2,317	175.00	125.37	1,274	164.81	113.95
Average	2,966	141.44	100	1,848	139.57	100	1,118	144.63	100
Annual rhythm	1,08	x	x	1,08	x	x	x	x	x

Source: N.I.S., 2019, Exports (FOB) by counties and by sections / chapters of the Combined Nomenclature (NC), <http://statistici.insse.ro:8077/tempo-online/>, Accessed on Feb.15, 2020 [4].

-The situation of the annual levels of the balance highlights the export / import relationship, the results of all the years being favorable. At the same time in the successive years, the favorable growth trend can be signaled. By comparison both with respect to the base year 2011, but also to the average of the period, there is a

maximum ceiling for the period 2013-2014 (this being between +36.7% and +39.35%).

Indeed, as can be seen from Fig. 3, it appears that the export / import activities for plant products have a tendency to manifest in parallel evolutionary form which are graphically rendered.

Fig. 3. Evolution of the import and export of plant products for the period 2011-2018 (Million Euro)

c) Foreign trade with live animals and animal products. They show annual levels whose oscillations have variable tendencies in the export / import situations. The values shown in Table 4 frame absolute and relative values by which the following can be highlighted:

- the export in the dynamics of the period analyzed by comparison with 2011, is represented by an annual increase (reaching + 33.56% in 2018), with variation levels at which the average of the period are different (between -25, 13% and + 21.28%). In this situation, the annual growth rate is 1.06%;

- for the import activities, higher values are registered, at which the level of 2018 compared to 2011 is + 83.83%. At the same time, the levels of variations compared to the average of the period are between -26,45% and + 35,21%. The annual import rate for this category of products is higher than for export, which is 1.09%;

- the balance that synthesizes the variations \pm of the export / import is negative for each year of the analyzed dynamics (comparative interpretations compared to 2011 and compared to average representing differentiated levels).

Table 4. Foreign trade with live animals and animal products from Romania, for the period 2011-2018

Year	Export			Import			Balance		
	Total mil €	% compared to:		mil €	% compared to:		mil €	% compared to:	
		2011	Mean		2011	Mean		2011	Mean
2011	584	100	74.87	965	100	73.55	-382	100	71.80
2012	731	125.17	93.71	1,035	107.25	78.88	-304	79.58	57.14
2013	745	127.56	95.51	1,114	115.44	84.90	-369	96.59	69.36
2014	743	127.22	95.25	1,226	127.04	93.44	-483	126.43	90.78
2015	782	133.90	100.25	1,254	129.94	95.57	-472	123.56	88.72
2016	814	139.38	104.35	1,441	149.32	109.83	-627	164.13	117.85
2017	946	161.98	121.28	1,689	175.02	128.73	-742	194.24	139.47
2018	895	153.25	114.74	1,774	183.83	135.21	-879	230.10	165.22
Average	780	133.56	100	1,312	135.95	100	-532	139.26	100
Annual rhythm	1,06	x		1,09	x	x	x	x	x

Source: N.I.S., 2019, Exports (FOB) by counties and by sections / chapters of the Combined Nomenclature (NC), <http://statistici.insse.ro:8077/tempo-online/>, Accessed on Feb.15, 2020 [4].

The curves shown in Fig. 4 show the tendency of the import level to exceed the export.

Fig. 4. Evolution of the import and export of live animals and animal products for the period 2011-2018 (Million Euro)

d) Foreign trade in food, beverages and tobacco. It represents a group of products that can be considered a significant evolution in foreign trade. In absolute and relative figures, rendered by the percentage-comparable forms, they

are presented in table 5 according to the dynamics of the 2011-2018 period, to which the following can be highlighted:

- the level of exports analyzed compared to the comparison year 2011, reflects an increase that in 2018 is + 62.96%, and compared to the average growth for the same year is + 17.21%. Throughout the period, the growth rate is 1.07%;

- the import reflects the same variational growth trend. It should be mentioned that these variation levels compared to 2011 recorded oscillations between + 10.15% and +76.45%. At the same time, it can be seen that, compared to the average period, the annual levels show oscillations, but they are between -24.86% and + 32.59%, the annual rate being 1.08.

Table 5. Foreign trade in food, beverages and tobacco in Romania, for the period 2011-2018

Year	Export			Import			Balance		
	Total mil €	% compared to:		mil €	% compared to:		mil €	% compared to:	
		2011	average		2011	average		2011	average
2011	1,099	100	71.92	1,911	100	75.14	-812	-100	80
2012	1,160	105.55	75.91	2,105	110.15	82.77	-945	-116.37	93.10
2013	1,315	119.65	86.06	2,177	113.91	85.60	-863	-106.28	85.02
2014	1,549	140.94	101.37	2,218	116.06	87.21	-668	-82.26	65.81
2015	1,838	167.24	120.28	2,580	135.00	101.45	-742	-91.37	73.10
2016	1,724	156.86	112.82	2,830	148.09	111.28	-1106	-136.20	108.96
2017	1,747	158.96	114.33	3,147	164.67	123.75	-1400	-172.41	137.93
2018	1,791	162.96	117.21	3,372	176.45	132.59	-1581	-194.70	155.76
Average	1,528	139.03	100	2,543	133.07	100	-1015	-125	100
Annual rhythm	1,07	x	x	1,08	x	x	x	x	x

Source: N.I.S., 2019, Exports (FOB) by counties and by sections / chapters of the Combined Nomenclature (NC), <http://statistici.insse.ro:8077/tempo-online/>, Accessed on Feb.15, 2020 [4].

The balance in this case of the of these products records for all the years negative levels, a situation caused by the existence of the higher levels of the import towards the export. The comparative percentage structures compared to 2011 also recorded negative values, at the same time with significant fluctuations compared to the period average (between -20.00% and + 55.76%).

Suggestively in Fig.5., these annual variations for export / import highlight the more pronounced trend of increasing the import.

Fig. 5. External evolution with food, beverages and tobacco, for 2011-2018 (Million Euro)

e) Foreign trade in animal or vegetable fats and oils. They are considered products with a much lower weight in the agri-food market and even in the decline phase. At the same time, in the foreign trade for these products, there is a mobility through the forms of the export / import activities, at which the value and percentage comparative form of the values are shown in table 6, where the following results: - with reference to the export values below the level of 2011 are found (between -24.39% and -0.83%), and by comparison with the average of the period results varying levels markedly differentiated (between -15.28% and +12, 03%). The annual rate itself is 0.99%;

-the import, which is maintained in this group of products, is recorded by levels below 2011 (between -39.07% and -2.45%), and by annual comparisons with the average period, oscillations are recorded that are between +23, 11% (2011 considered the first year of the analyzed dynamics) and -17.59% (2014). Even with the existence of these oscillations during the analyzed period, a growth rate of 0.95% is maintained;

- the analysis of the levels of the balance presented according to the values rendered in million € shows the existence of a negative level only in the first two years (2011 and 2012), after which for the rest of the years of the same period (2013-2018) the values are positive. Comparisons with 2011 show positive values only in 2012, after which (in the comparison years 2013-2018) these balance sheets are negative. Comparative levels compared to the average of the period

show variations similar to those obtained from the dynamics of value analysis in € million (negative in 2011-2012 and positive in 2013-2018).

Table 6. Foreign trade in animal or vegetal fats and oils from Romania, for the period 2011-2018

Year	Export			Import			Balance			
	Total mil €	% compared to:		mil €			Total mil €	% compared to:		
		2011	average		2011	average		2011	average	
2011	242	100	112.03	245	100	123.11	-4	100	-23.52	
2012	183	75.61	84.72	239	97.55	120.10	-56	1,400	-329.41	
2013	240	99.17	111.11	205	83.67	103.01	34	-850	200	
2014	213	88.01	98.61	164	66.93	82.41	49	-	1,225	288.23
2015	224	92.56	103.70	184	75.10	92.46	40	-	1,000	235.29
2016	194	80.16	89.81	189	77.14	94.97	5	-125	29.41	
2017	211	87.19	97.68	192	78.36	96.48	19	-475	111.76	
2018	224	92.56	103.70	172	70.20	86.43	52	-	1,300	305.88
Average	216	89.25	100	199	81.22	100	17	-425	100	
Annual rhythm	0,99	x	x	0,95	x	x	x	x	x	

Source: N.I.S., 2019, Exports (FOB) by counties and by sections / chapters of the Combined Nomenclature (NC), <http://statistici.insse.ro:8077/tempo-online/>, Accessed on Feb.15, 2020 [4].

Fig. 6. Evolution of foreign trade in animal or vegetable fats and oils, for the period 2011-2018 (Million Euro)

It turns out that for the foreign trade the variational ensemble analyzed in the successive years for the products of fats and oils, there is a tendency of increase of

the export with regard to the import (the form of this tendency can be noticed by the tendency shown in Fig.6.

Conclusions

From the analysis of the foreign trade activities for the main groups of agri-food products in Romania, according to the indicators in absolute and percentage-comparative values, the following can be summarized:

(1). The levels of the foreign trade activity in the agri-food field reflect annual variations, in which the average levels compared to the total period analyzed are of 9-10%. At the same time, the value and percentage-comparative levels of the balances highlight the existence of negative situations for all the years of the period analyzed, both for the whole country and for the whole group of agri-food products.

(2). Regarding the foreign trade activities classified in the group of vegetable products, there is an annual rhythm of the increase of the export which has determined favorable levels of balance. At the same time, from the balance sheet analysis of the foreign trade of these products, according to the comparative situations with respect to the base year 2011 and the average of the period, it indicates an increasing tendency.

(3).The external trade with live animals and animal products shows for all the years a lower level of export vis-à-vis the import, which results in an unfavorable balance. Compared to the same product group, we can see (compared to 2011 and the average period) levels within an annual growth rate.

(4). Framed in significant levels the group of food, beverages and tobacco, frames a tendency in which the import is predominant in the annual structure of the whole period analyzed. As such, the balance in the case of these products records for all the years negative levels, although in the analysis of the comparative forms, compared to the base year 2011 and the average of the period, it shows a tendency of growth.

(5). Products classified as animal or vegetable fats and oils, although they have a much lower weight in the whole of foreign trade with agri-food products, indicate for most years a tendency to favor the balance. This results from the variation in annual levels, which results in a decrease in imports, for which annual exports maintain a relatively constant level.

Foreign trade analyzed by the structure of the value and percentage levels of the main groups of agri-food products can be deduced the following: only vegetable products and oils / fats show a certain tendency of favorability (export> import), to which is added the group of live animal products / animal products and of food

/ beverages/tobacco for which unfavorable tendencies are manifest (export< import). In conclusion for the national level, the problem is raised of some concerns from which result the export profitability especially to the products classified to live animals and animal products, concluding the necessity of the growth in a more accentuated rate of the degree of valorization of the agri-food products, expressed in this work through export value.

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ASSESSMENT OF PERMANENT GRASSLAND PRODUCTIVITY IN POIANA RUSCĂ MOUNTAINS (SOUTH- WEST ROMANIAN CARPATHIANS)

Teodor MARUȘCA¹, Gicu Gabriel ARSENE², Elena TAULESCU³

Abstract. *The paper presents an application of a new method of evaluating the productivity of permanent grasslands based on the abundance-dominance and frequency data of the species from the floristically studies. Nine vegetation associations of representative grasslands from the Poiana Ruscă Mountains were studied, for which the pastoral value was evaluated for the forage quality. This indicator ranges from 5.0 for As. *Viola declinatae* - *Nardetum* up to 88.3 for As. *Trifolio repenti-Lolietum perennis*, being on average 36.7, mediocre in appreciation. The production of useful fresh phytomass is generally low, being on average 6.62 t/ha green matter, from 0.61 t/ha to 18.63 t/ha in the same phytocenoses mentioned for the pastoral value. Based on these results, the optimal grazing capacity of the permanent grasslands in the study area can be determined.*

Keywords: permanent grasslands, pastoral value, fresh matter yield, Poiana Ruscă

1. Introduction

In the mountainous area, which occupies about a third of Romania's national area, there are permanent meadows with an important role in animal husbandry, especially sheep and cattle. (Bărbulescu & Motcă, 1983) [2]. For a better management of this pastoral patrimony, in addition to the vegetation inventory studies, it is necessary to evaluate the productivity of the meadows, respectively the quality and the fodder production.

The assessment of the meadow yield is usually done on fenced areas where the grass is sown and weighed and quality analyses are performed in the laboratory. This method requires high costs of fencing and guarding them in isolated areas, being impossible to apply in the Romanian Carpathians, in most cases. For these reasons, we have developed a new method for evaluating the productivity of meadows based on floristic survey (phytosociological relevés) Marușca (2019) [7].

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Through this method, the former results of the vegetation studies on permanent meadows can be capitalized on a higher level for practice, and can then be used for the elaboration of the pastoral management plans and further, to orient the meadows improvement strategies.

2. Material and Method

To exemplify the new method, we conducted a case study on data from the doctoral thesis "Ecological and phytocenological study of grassy grassland vegetation in the Poiana Ruscă Mountains" (Arsene, 1998) [1].

In this paper we described 9 more frequent phytocenoses of grasslands as follows (according to the current 1998 Romanian synsystematics):

Cl. FESTUCO – BROMETEA, Br-BI 1943 et Tx. 1943

Ord. *FESTUCETALIA VALESIIACAE*, Br-BI et Tx., 1943

Al. *Festucion rupicolae* Soó 1940

As. *Agrostideto capillaris* - *Festucetum rupicolae* M.Cs.-Kaptalan(1962) 1964

As. *Botriochloetum (Andropogonetum) ischaemi* (Krist 1937), I.Pop 1977

As. *Brometum (Zernetum) fibrosi* Roman 1974

Cl. MOLINIO – ARRHENATHERETEA Tx 1937

Ord. *ARRHENATHERETALIA* Pawl, 1928

Al. *Cynosurion* Tx., 1947

As. *Festuco rubrae-Agrostitetum capillaris* Horv. 1951

Ord. *MOLINIETALIA COERULAE* Boşcaiu 1965

Al. *Molinion coeruleae* W.Koch 1926

As. *Peucedano rocheliani* - *Molinietalia coeruleae* Boşcaiu 1965

Cl. NARDO - CALLUNETEA Prsg 1949

Ord. *NARDETALIA* Oberd 1949

Al. *Potentillo* - *Nardion* Simon 1957

As. *Violo declinatae* - *Nardetum* Simon 1966

Cl. TRIFOLIO - GERANIETEA SANGUINEI Müll. 1961

Ord. *Origanetalia* Müll. 1961

Al. *Trifolion medii* Müll. 1961

As. *Clinopodio* - *Pteridietum aquilini* Dihoru 1975

Cl. PLANTAGINETEA MAJORIS Tx.et Prsg. 1950

Ord. *PLANTAGINETALIA MAJORIS* Tx (1947) 1950

Al. *Agropyro* - *Rumicion crispi* Nordh.1040

As.*Trifolio repenti-Lolietum perennis* Krippelova 1957

To estimate the productivity of permanent grasslands, we proceeded to transform the Braun-Blanquet abundance-dominance (AD) notes in percentage of coverage -

participation (P %) in order to further perform statistical calculations. In this sense, we used a transformation matrix from the AD scale notes to P% values, developed by Marușca (2019) [7], Table 1.

Table 1. Conversion matrix of the Abundance-Dominance notes (A-D) and of the values of average constancy (K %) from the phytosociological tables in values of species participation (P %), or coverage (according to Marușca 2019 [7], revised)

Braun-Blanquet A-D scale notes	AD based on K (%)				
	K class V (81% – 100%)	K class IV (61%– 80%)	K class III (41%– 60%)	K class II (21%– 40%)	K class I (<20%)
5	87.5*	61.3	43.8	26.3	8.8
4 - 5	75.0	52.5	37.5	22.5	7.5
3 - 5	62.5	43.8	31.3	18.8	6.3
2 - 5	52.5	36.8	26.3	15.8	5.3
1 - 5	46.3	32.4	23.2	13.9	4.6
+ - 5	44.0	30.8	22.0	13.2	4.4
4	62.5*	43.8	31.3	18.8	6.3
3 - 4	50.0	35.0	25.0	15.0	5.0
2 - 4	40.0	28.0	20.0	12.0	4.0
1 - 4	33.8	23.7	16.9	10.1	3.4
+ - 4	31.5	22.1	15.8	9.5	3.2
3	37.5*	26.3	18.9	11.3	3.8
2 - 3	27.5	19.3	13.8	8.3	2.8
1 - 3	21.3	14.9	10.7	6.4	2.1
+ - 3	19.0	13.3	9.5	5.7	1.9
2	17.5*	12.3	8.8	5.3	1.8
1 - 2	11.3	7.9	5.7	3.4	1.1
+ - 2	9.0	6.3	4.5	2.7	0.9
1	5.0*	3.5	2.5	1.5	0.5
+ - 1	2.8	2.0	1.4	0.8	0.3
+	0.5*	0.4	0.3	0.2	0.1

*) Correspondence of the AD Braun-Blanquet scale in coverage percentages, according to Tüxen and Ellenberg (1937, in Cristea *et al.*, 2004 [3]).

The pastoral value (PV) of each plant association was calculated using the formula:

$$PV = \Sigma P (\%) \times F/9$$

where:

F is the feed quality index according to (Kovacs (1979) [4], Păcurar & Rotar (2014) [8], and Marușca (2019) [7]):

F1 = toxic plants for animals and humans;

F2 = plants harmful to animal products;

F3 = weeds harmful to the meadows vegetal carpet;

F4 = low fodder plants (ballast);
 F5 = mediocre forage plants (previously considered F1 on a 5-step scale);
 F6 = medium fodder plants (former category F2);
 F7 = good fodder plants (formerly F3);
 F8 = very good fodder plants (formerly F4);
 F9 = excellent fodder plants (formerly F5).

Only species with F indices values from 4 to 9 (F4 to F9) entered the calculation for the evaluation of PV, the remaining F₁ to F₃ are considered harmful.

The PV values assessment is as follows:

0 - 5 degraded meadow (Deg.); 40 - 60 middle (Middle);
 5 - 15 very low (VL); 60 - 80 good (G);
 15 - 25 low (L); 80 - 100 very good (VG).
 25 - 40 mediocre (Med.);

The production of useful phytomass or consumable green fodder (CGF) was estimated considering only the species with F4 to F9+, by multiplying the P% value with a plant habitus coefficient (M), having values from 1 (very small) to 9 (very high), thus establishing a weighted IM index value (Marușca 2016, 2019) [5, 6]. The final evaluation of the CGF is made by multiplying the IM habitus index value with other indices values established in meadow experiments, according to Table 2.

Table 2. Correspondence between the values of the production indices of the species (IM) and the estimated consumable green fodder (CGF) (according to Marușca, 2019 [7])

IM values	Conversion coefficients in CGF	Estimated CGF (t/ha)	Productivity class
0.1 – 0.5	x 1.8	0.2 – 0.9	very low
0.5 – 1.0	x 1.9	1.0 – 1.9	
1.0 – 1.5	x 2.0	2.0 – 3.0	low
1.5 – 2.0	x 2.1	3.2 – 4.2	
2.0 – 2.5	x 2.2	4.4 – 5.5	low - middle
2.5 – 3.0	x 2.3	5.8 – 6.9	
3.0 – 3.5	x 2.4	7.2 – 8.4	middle
3.5 – 4.0	x 2.5	8.8 – 10.0	
4.0 – 4.5	x 2.6	10.4 – 11.7	middle-good
4.5 – 5.0	x 2.7	12.2 – 13.5	
5.0 – 5.5	x 2.8	14.0 – 15.4	good
5.5 – 6.0	x 2.9	16.0 – 17.4	
6.0 – 6.5	x 3.0	18.0 – 19.5	good-very good
6.5 – 7.0	x 3.1	20.2 – 21.7	
7.0 – 7.5	x 3.2	22.4 – 24.0	very good
7.5 – 8.0	x 3.3	24.8 – 26.4	
8.0 – 8.5	x 3.4	27.2 – 28.9	excellent
8.5 – 9.0	x 3.5	29.8 – 31.5	

The value of CGF thus calculated varies greatly, from 0.2, for degraded meadows, to 31.5 t / ha, for extensively used meadows.

3. Results and Discussions

The pastoral value (PV) as a quality indicator of the phytocenoses studied is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. The permanent meadows pastoral value of the phytocenoses in the Poiana Ruscă Mountains

Phytocenosis type	Pastoral value (PV)	Difference + -	% from the mean	PV appreciation
Al. <i>Festucion rupicolae</i> (mean)	29.4	-7.3	80	Mediocre
As. <i>Agrostideto capillaris-Festucetum rupicolae</i>	61.1	+24.4	166	Good
As. <i>Botriochloetum ischaemi</i>	15.1	-21.6	41	Low
As. <i>Brometum fibrosi</i>	12.1	-24.6	33	Very low
Al. <i>Cynosurion</i>				
As. <i>Festuco rubrae-Agrostietum capillaris</i>	28.7	+65.4	178	Good
Al. <i>Violo declinatae-Nardion</i>				
As. <i>Violo declinatae-Nardetum</i>	5.0	-31.7	14	Degraded
Al. <i>Trifolion medii</i>				
As. <i>Clinopodio-Pteridietum</i>	6.7	-30.0	18	Very low
Al. <i>Agropyro-Rumicion</i>				
As. <i>Trifolio repenti-Lolietum perennis</i>	88.3	+51.6	241	Very good
Al. <i>Molinion coeruleae</i>				
As. <i>Peucedano-Molinietum</i>	30.8	-5.9	84	Mediocre
Al. <i>Potentillion anserinae</i>				
As. <i>Junco inflexi-Menthetum longifoliae</i>	46.1	+9.4	126	Middle
Mean	36.7	0	100	Mediocre

Considering that 8 phytosociological alliances are each represented by only one association and only one, *Festucion rupicolae*, has 3 subordinates, the assessment of the pastoral value was made at the alliance level which is generally assimilated with the habitat for the permanent meadows. On average, the meadows in the Poiana Ruscă Mountains have a pastoral value of 36.7, considered as mediocre, with variations from 5.0 (degraded) for *Violo declinatae - Nardion* to 88.3 (very good) for *Agropyro - Rumicion* with the most valuable forage species such as *Lolium perenne* and *Trifolium repens*. Good pastoral value is recorded for the As. *Agrostideto capillaris - Festucetum rupicolae*, with PV over 60, the rest of PV values being lower.

By comparison, the average pastoral value of the phytocenoses in the Poiana Ruscă Mountains, which is 36.7, is 5% better than that of the phytocenoses in the Măcin Mountains, where an average PV value of 35.0 was evaluated (Maruşca *et al.*, 2019) [7].

The CGF of the phytocenoses from the Poiana Ruscă Mountains follows the same trend as the pastoral value to which it is directly related proportionally (Table 4).

Table 4. Estimated CGF of permanent grassland phytocenoses in the Poiana Rusca Mountains

Phytocenosis type	Useful phytomass index (IM)	Coefficients of transformation in CGF	CGF (t /ha)	% compared to the mean	CGF appreciation
Al. Festucion rupicolae					
<i>As. Agrostideto capillaris-Festucetum rupicolae</i>	4.42	2.6	11.49	174	Middle
<i>As. Botriochloetum ischaemi</i>	0.96	1.9	1.82	27	Very low
<i>As. Brometum fibrosi</i>	0.89	1.9	1.69	26	Very low
Al. Cynosurion					
<i>As. Festuco rubrae-Agrostietum capillaris</i>	4.47	2.6	11,62	176	Middle
Al. Violo declinatae-Nardion					
<i>As. Violo declinatae-Nardetum</i>	0.34	1.8	0.61	9	Very low
Al. Trifolion medii					
<i>As. Clinopodio-Pteridietum</i>	0.41	1.8	0.74	11	Very low
Al. Agropyro-Rumicion					
<i>As. Trifolio repenti-Lolietum perennis</i>	6.21	3.0	18.63	281	Very low
Al. Molinion coeruleae					
<i>As. Peucedano-Molinietum</i>	1,94	2,1	4,07	61	Low
Al. Potentillion anserinae					
<i>As. Junco inflexi-Menthetum longifoliae</i>	3.55	2.5	8.88	134	Middle
MEAN	2.55	2.6	6.62	100	Low

The highest CGF, of 18.63 t/ha, is estimated for the *As. Trifolio repenti-Lolietum perennis*, and the lowest (0.61 t/ha) at *As. Violo declinatae-Nardetum*.

The CGF values, around 11.5 t/ha, were estimated for the *As. Agrostideto capillaris-Festucetum rupicolae* and *As. Festuco rubrae-Agrostietum capillaris*, otherwise the yields are lower.

The average production of grassland phytocenoses in the Poiana Rusca Mountains is 6.62 t/ha, 12% higher than those in the Macinului Mountains where 5.89 t/ha was assessed (Marușca *et al.* 2019) [7], in both situations being considered as low yields.

Conclusions

- (1). Assessing the productivity of permanent meadows (quality and yield) is necessary for the preparation of pastoral management plans and further for the scientific management of this land category of agricultural use.
- (2). The pastoral value and CGF assessment on the basis of floristic surveys proved to be a rather expeditious and precise method in comparison with other more expensive and difficult to apply methods.
- (3). The meadows in the Poiana Ruscă Mountains present extremely varied pastoral values, from 5.0 (degraded) to 88.3 (very good), and an equally inhomogeneous CGF, from 0.61 t/ha to 18.63 t/ha, on average 6.62 t/ha, being considered low, needing to be further managed properly.
- (4). The method proposed by us (Marușca, 2019) [6], has a good potential for generalization in Romania and also for refining so as to allow more quick, precise and low time and resources consuming assessments of meadows yield.

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CONTRIBUTIONS ON THE ESTABLISHMENT OF PRODUCTIVITY INDICATORS FOR COW MILK PRODUCED IN THE CARPATHIAN MOUNTAINS

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Abstract. *Assessing the productivity of a pasture in animal product, such as live weight gain or milk production, is very important for establishing creditworthiness levels, planning, valorisation, fees, subsidies, etc. In an experience with dairy cows on an improved pasture, in the Bucegi Mountains, located at 1,800 m altitude, after 20 years, a coefficient of correlation statistically assured between pastoral value and milk production in the grazing season has been determined. Using this coefficient of 51.24 by multiplying it by the pastoral value, it is possible to directly estimate the milk yield per hectare of an improved pasture exploited in a rational way. For the mountain area with usual precipitations, this coefficient has a gradient of - 4.5 / 100 m altitude, respectively from 98, for 600 - 800 m with a duration of 160 grazing days, to 35 for 2,000 – 2,200 m m, where dairy cows graze for an average of 55 summering days.*

Keywords: pastoral value, grazing, cows, milk production coefficient, altitudinal gradient

1. Introduction

The mountain pastures in the Carpathians represent the main fodder source for raising sheep and cattle (Bărbulescu, Motcă 1983, Burcea et al. 2007) [1,2]. The expression of the productivity of pastures utilised by grazing in animal production is the most faithful economic indicator. In this sense, experiments were initiated with young bulls in which the increase in live weight was recorded (Vladeni, Persani Mountains 600 m alt.) And with cows in which milk was measured (Moroieni, Bucegi Mountains, 1,800 m alt.) (Marușca 1973 , Marușca et al. 2002) [4,5].

Obviously, these animal experiments are more difficult to carry out in the mountain area, so it is necessary to evaluate animal production by indirect means

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such as floristic composition and the calculation of pastoral value. Such a case-by-case approach set out to present this paper.

2. Material and Method

In order to achieve the proposed objectives, the data of the animal experience started in 1996 in Bucegi were analyzed. These trials are continuing at the moment.

By comparing the pastoral value calculated on the basis of floristic composition, with the milk cow production in the grazing season, the statistically ensured coefficient 51.24 was established (Maruşca et al.2018) [6].

Thus, by multiplying the pastoral value by 51.24 established for the subalpine pastures from 1,800 m, it is possible to evaluate with quite high accuracy the milk production per hectare in the conditions of management and rational use of these permanent grasslands. From the level of 1,800 m above sea level (a.s.l.) where the long-term experience with dairy cows has been established, gradients were outlined up and down for each 100 m, during the grazing season and the milk production coefficient.

The case study for the application of this transformation coefficient in milk production were the associations of permanent sub mountain and mountain grasslands in Northern Oltenia (Ionescu et al.2001) [3].

This application demonstrates the validity of this assesement system of animal production in mountain pastures.

3. Results and Discussions

The duration of the optimal grazing season at 600 - 800 m alt. it is about 160 days and decreases by 7.5 days for every 100 m altitude to 2,000 - 2,200 m, where it reaches only 55 days (Table 1).

Table 1. Production of cow milk for an average pastoral value of 50, depending on altitude

Altitude	Grazing season length, (days)	Correlation coefficient	Milk production (L / ha)
2,000 - 2,200	55	35	1,750
1,800 - 2,000	70	44	2,200
1,600 - 1,800	85	53	2,650
1,400 - 1,600	100	62	3,100
1,200 - 1,400	115	71	3,550
1,000 - 1,200	130	80	4,000
800 - 1,000	145	89	4,450
600 - 800	160	98	4,900
Gradients / 100 m	- 7.5	- 4.5	- 225

On the same altitudinal amplitude, the coefficient of transformation of the pastoral value in milk production varies from 98 at 600 - 800 m to 35 at 2,000 - 2,200 m, with a gradient of - 4.5 / 100 m altitude.

If the pastoral value were 50 on the entire altitudinal amplitude of 1,400 m, applying the transformation coefficient for milk production it reaches 4,900 liters / hectare at 600 - 800 m up to 1,750 l / ha at 2,000 - 2,200 m, with a gradient of - 225 liters / 100 m alt.

For example, in order to express the pastoral value in cow milk production, it is presented for the associations of sub mountain and mountain pastures in Northern Oltenia (Table 2).

Table 2. Evaluation of cow milk production for the main associations of sub mountain and mountain pastures in Northern Oltenia

Phytosociological association	Pastoral Value (VP)	Milk Production (L/ha)	Relative Production (%)
A. Mountain grasslands (600 - 1,600 m alt.), 130 grazing season days and 80 coefficient of transformation into milk			
1. <i>Trifolio(repenti) - Lolietum perennis</i>	86.7	6,935	141
2. <i>Festuco (rubrae) - Agrostitetum capillaris</i>	63.8	5,105	104
3. <i>Danthonio - Festucetum rubrae</i>	59.9	4,790	97
4. <i>Agrosti(capillaris) - Chrysopogonetum grylli</i>	46.3	3,945	80
5. <i>Agrosti(capillaris) - Festucetum rubrae</i>	57.8	4,625	94
6. <i>Agrosti(capillaris) - Genistelletum</i>	51.6	4,130	84
Average A:	61.5	4,920	100
B. Subalpine and alpine pastures (1,600 - 2,200 m alt.), 70 grazing season days and 44 medium coefficient of transformation into milk			
1. <i>Potentillo (ternatae) - Festucetum airoides</i>	46.1	2,030	135
2. <i>Scorzonero (rosae) - Festucetum nigrescentis</i>	33.4	1,470	98
3. <i>Seslerio (coerulantis) - Festucetum saxatilis</i>	38.3	1,685	112
4. <i>Seslerio (bielzii) - Caricetum sempervirentis</i>	34.3	1,510	100
5. <i>Primulo (minimae) - Caricetum curvulae</i>	39.6	1,740	114
6. <i>Violo (declinatae) - Nardetum strictae</i>	13.5	595	40
Average B:	34.2	1,505	100
Difference B - A:	+ , - →		
	% →	- 27.3	- 3,415
		56	69
General Average AB	47.8	3,210	x

From these data it results that the type of *Lolium perenne* with *Trifolium repens* grasslands from riversides with a pastoral value of 86.7 can produce over 6,900 liters of cow milk per hectare under appropriate management and utilization conditions, similar to Western European productions.

At the opposite pole is the type of grass degraded by *Nardus stricta* species in the high mountains with a pastoral value of 13.5 and a milk production close of 600 liters per hectare.

Under normal conditions of maintenance and operation, mountain pastures can provide on average 4,900 l / ha and on subalpine and alpine ones 1,500 l / ha, more than 3 times less.

On the entire amplitude from 600 to 2,200 m a.s.l., the pastoral value average of permanent pastures in northern Oltenia is close to 50 and the possible milk production reaches 3,200 l / ha, under normal management conditions.

Conclusions

- (1). The evaluation of cow milk production achieved on pastures during the grazing season is an important indicator for the pastoral economy.
- (2). By applying a coefficient of transformation after establishing the pastoral value based on the floristic composition, it is possible to predict with sufficient accuracy the milk production potential, per hectare of pasture.
- (3). The production of cow milk on the pastures in northern Oltenia varies between 600 liters per hectare on the associations with *Nardus stricta* species, from the high mountains, up to 6,900 liters per hectare on the association *Lolium perenne* with *Trifolium repens* species from riversides.

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TRENDS IN SHEEP AND GOAT LIVESTOCK AND MEAT PRODUCTION CONCENTRATION AND THEIR ECONOMIC IMPACT IN ROMANIA IN THE PERIOD 2009-2018

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Abstract. *The concentration of sheep and goats livestock and meat production were studied in Romania in the period 2009-2018 using the data provided by the National Institute of Statistics, Herfindhal-Hirschman (HHI) and Gini-Struck (GSI) indices, trend analysis, and structural changes. The results pointed out both the livestock and the live weight for slaughtering increase by 16.5 %, and, respectively, by 10.9%. Sheep and goats livestock is moderately concentrated in five micro-regions: Centre, South East, North West, North East, and West (81%), while meat production in terms of live weight is concentrated mainly in South East, Centre, South Muntenia, North West and North East as proved by HHI (0.1494-0.1654) and GSI(0.4132-0.4467) values. The concentration growth has a positive influence on export which accounted of 93% of production and on export/import ratio which reflected that Romania has an efficient international trade with this product, being a net exporting country.*

Keywords: sheep and goats, livestock, meat production, concentration, economic impact, Romania

1. Introduction

Sheep and goat meat are high value sources of nutrients and energy which could nourish our body and maintain its health.

In 100 g of sheep meat, there are: 20 g proteins, 6.5 g fats, water 72 %, and 144 kilocalories, while in 100 g of lamb meat there are: 18 g proteins, 20 g fats, vitamins (B and C), minerals (calcium, iron), 62 % water, and 260 kilocalories (Damian, 2017)[1]. In 100 g goat meat, there are: 27 g proteins, 30.5 g fats (linoleic acid, a lower content of saturated fatty acids), vitamins (A, B6, B12, C, D, E, K) and minerals (calcium, potassium, selenium, iron, a lower content of sodium) and 143 calories, and for this reason it is a healthy meat preventing cancer, anemia, osteoporosis, heart diseases, stimulating brain activity and sustaining immunity (Vasiliu Alina, 2020) [18].

Sheep and goat meat consumption is not so high, but it is continuously growing in the recent decade due to the changes in consumer's new orientation for a healthy diet, the better quality of meat products from these two species resulting from the

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progress in animal science and technology, production systems, animal slaughtering and meat processing, carcass grading which determine a high food quality and safety (Teixeira et al, 2019) [17].

Sheep meat is preferred and consumed especially in Australia, New Zealand, United Kingdom, Argentina and in the Arabian and African countries with a long tradition in production and consumption (Skapetas and Bampidis, 2016) [16].

Despite that goat meat is an important source of food for a growing human population, demand and offer are still low, being higher in the developing countries. However, in the Western countries, consumers look to be more and more aware of goat meat benefits for health because it is a lean meat with a low fat and cholesterol content compared to other meat types (Webb, 2014)[19].

At present, of the total global goat meat output, China produces 39%, followed by India 9%, Pakistan 6%, Nigeria 4%, Bangladesh 4%, Australia 1%, others 38% (Meat and Livestock Australia, Global Snapshot I Goat meat, 2020)[5].

The global total meat production (in carcass equivalent) is expected to reach 357.4 million tons by the year 2025. Sheep and goat meat output will also increase and is expected to be 17.5 million tons in 2025. The main contributors will be China by 45 % and Sub Saharian Africa by 27% (FAO, OECD, 2016) [4].

In the EU, the sheep and goat livestock increased reaching a peak in 2016 of 99.8 million sheep and 97.8 million goats, but then it started to decline to 97.8 million sheep and 94 million goats in 2018.

In this year, the main EU countries raising sheep were Greece (15.85 million), United Kingdom (22.28 million) and Romania (10,176 million). The main countries growing goats were: Spain (2,76 million) and Romania (1.54 million).

Sheep and goats bring an important contribution to the EU milk and meat production besides poultry, pigs and bovines (Popescu Agatha, 2013b)[11].

The EU-28 sheep and goat meat production accounted for 776 thousand tons carcass, the same level like in 2017, of which: United Kingdom 37.2%, Spain 16.8%, France 11.3%, Greece 9 % and Ireland 8.8%. Of the 0.8 million tons meat from the both species, sheep meat accounts for 90%. (Eurostat, 2020; Popescu Agatha, 2017) [3, 14].

Romania has a long tradition in raising sheep and goats and occupies an important position in the EU for its livestock. Sheep and goats are raised in Romania for milk, meat and wool. Sheep and goats contribute by 3.6 % to milk production and by 8 % to meat production (Popescu Agatha, 2017, Popescu Agatha et al, 2020) [14, 15].

However, sheep and goat meat is ranked the fourth in meat consumption after pork, poultry meat and beef (Pirvutoiu and Popescu, 2013; Popescu, 2013a, Popsecu Agatha, 2016) [7, 10, 13].

In this context, the purpose of the study was to analyze the trends in the livestock and meat production concentration during the period 2009-2018 and to assess their economic impact.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Data collection

The empirical data have been picked up from various sources such as: National Institute of Statistics, Eurostat Statistics Explained, FAO, etc for the period 2009-2018 [3, 4, 6].

2.2. The main specific indicators taken into consideration

The main indicators taken into account have been: sheep and goat livestock at the national level and by micro-region, livestock structure by micro region, sheep and goat meat production in terms of live weight for slaughtering for consumption at the national level and in the territory by micro-region, the contribution of the micro-regions to the meat output, the concentration degree of the sheep and goat livestock and meat production, the economic impact in terms of the share of export in the meat output and the export/import ratio as main indicators reflecting the international trade efficiency of the country.

2.3. Methodological aspects

The dynamics of the indicators reflecting increase or decline on the whole interval was analyzed using the Fixed Index, $IFB = (X_n / X_1) * 100$, where: X = the variable taken into consideration, $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, i$, the years of the chronological series, the year 2009 was considered equal to 100 as being term of reference, regression polynomial equation $Y = ax^2 + bx + c$, for reflecting the sinuous dynamics of meat production, concentration degree was evaluated based on the use of the well known Herfindhal-Hirschman Index (HHI), having the formula: $HHI = \sum_{i=1}^n (g_i)^2$ and Gin-Struck Index (GSI) having the formula:

$$GSI = \sqrt{\frac{n \sum_{i=1}^n g_i^2 - 1}{n-1}}$$

$$\text{where: } g_i = \frac{X_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n X_i} = \frac{X_i}{X_j}$$

i = the micro-region of development, $i = 1, 2, \dots, 8$

X_i = the analyzed indicator in the micro-region i

X_j = the total level of the indicator at the national level

g_i = the share of the micro -region i in the total national level, X_j

Meat Food Balance was determined as follows: Production (P) plus Import (I) minus Export (E) = Offer (O), according to the formula: $O = P + I - E$.

The ratio Export/Production, E/P was calculated dividing the export amount by meat production.

The Export/Import ratio was determined dividing the exported amount by the imported amount (Popescu Agatha, 2010) [8].

All calculations and graphic illustrations were made using the Excel facilities.

3. Results and discussions

3.1. Dynamics of sheep and goats livestock

In 2018, Romania had 11,715,717 sheep and goats, of which 10,176,400 sheep (86.86%) and 1,539,317 goats (13.14%), all together meaning a surplus of 16.5% compared to 2009 (Fig.1).

Fig.1. Dynamic of sheep and goats livestock, Romania (Million heads)
Source: Own design based on NIS data, 2020.

3.2. Number of agricultural holdings growing sheep and goats

In general, the farms raising sheep have also goats. In 2018, there were 287,865 holdings growing sheep and taking into account the number of animals, this means 35.3 heads average flock size per farm. About 63% of the sheep farms are raising about 12 % of the whole sheep livestock, they are small individual farms with an average flock below 10 heads, grown in an extensive system. About 6.5 %

of the livestock is grown in larger farms whose average flock size is about 15,5 heads, where also the extensive system is practiced. Only about 10,850 sheep, representing 3.8% of the total sheep farms are raising over 200 heads, with an average flock size of about 400 heads.

3.3. Dispersion of sheep and goat livestock in the territory

The distribution of the sheep and goats livestock in the territory is not equal. In 2018, the regions with the highest number of sheep were the following ones: Centre (22.7%), North West (16.8%), South East (15.1%), West (15%) and North East (13.9%), summing 83.5%.

The highest number of goats was raised in South East (25.3%), South West Oltenia (19.8%), South Muntenia (17.5%), and North East (15.3%), totalling 76.9% of the goat livestock.

The largest sheep and goat livestock was found in the Central part (21%), South East (16.4%), North West (15.6%), North East (14.2%) and West (13.5%) (Table 1).

Table 1. The share of micro regions in sheep and goat livestock in 2018 versus 2009 (%)

	Sheep by micro region (%)		Goats by micro region (%)		Sheep and goats by micro region (%)	
	2009	2018	2009	2018	2009	2018
NW	15.2	16.8	8.7	7.7	14.6	15.6
C	19.5	22.7	9.5	9.2	18.6	21.0
NE	17.3	13.9	14.1	15.3	17.0	14.2
SE	16.4	15.1	24.5	25.3	17.2	16.4
S Munt.	10.1	9.6	16.9	17.5	10.8	10.6
B If	0.3	0.2	0.9	0.8	0.3	0.3
SW Olt.	7.8	6.7	20.0	18.8	8.9	8.3
W	13.4	15	5.4	5.4	12.5	13.5

Source: Own calculation based on NIS data, 2020.

The distribution of sheep and goat growing in the territory is closely linked to the favourable local conditions regarding soil and climate condition, forage resources, the existence of pastures and meadows, breed structure, technical aspects etc. (Popescu Agatha, 2012) [9].

3.4. Dynamics of live weight of sheep and goats for slaughtering for consumption

In the analyzed period 2009-2018, the live weight and the sheep and goats for slaughtering increased by 10.9% from 104.3 thousand tons in 2009 to 115.7 thousand tons in 2018. This was due to the growth registered in the number of sheep and goats and to the gain in the growing and fattening period (Fig.2).

Fig.2. Dynamic of sheep and goats live weight for slaughtering, Romania (Thousand tons)
Source: Own design based on NIS data, 2020.

The contribution of sheep and goats to the live weight of the slaughtered animals in Romania increased to 7.2 % in 2009 to 8 % in 2018, being situated on the 4th position after poultry (42.3%), pigs (37%) and bovines (12.6%) (Popescu Agatha, 2013c; NIS, 2020) [12, 6].

3.5. Dispersion of sheep and goats live weight in the territory

In 2018, the regions which recorded the highest live weight of sheep and goats for slaughtering were: South East (24.4%), Centre (18.6%), South Muntenia (15.1%), North West (12.3%) and North East (11.7%) (Table 2).

If we compare the dispersion of the live weight with the dispersion of the livestock by micro region, we may easily find out that:

- despite the Central region has the highest number of sheep and goats, being on the 1st position, it is situated on the 2nd position for the live weight;
- the South East micro region situated on the 2nd position for livestock is on the 1st position for live weight;

-the North West region ranked the 3rd for live stock comes on the 4th position for live weight;

-the North East region situated on the 4th position for livestock comes on the 5th position for live weight;

- finally, the West region ranked the 5th for live stock comes on the 6th position for live weight.

This is due to the breed structure existing in various regions, climate conditions, availability of forage resources, growing systems practiced in various farms.

Table 2. The share of micro regions in the sheep and goats live weight in 2018 versus 2009 (%)

	2009	2018
NW	12.5	12.3
C	17.9	18.6
NE	13.7	11.7
SE	11.4	24.4
S Munt.	12.8	15.1
B If	0.3	0.4
SW Olt.	8.4	6.3
W	11.9	11.2

Source: Own calculation based on NIS data, 2020.

3.6. Concentration degree in terms of HHI and GSI

The values of Herfindahl-Hirschman Index varied between 0.1496, the minimum level registered in 2009, and 0.1567 recorded in 2010, the maximum level. HHI characterized a modest concentration in 2009 ($HHI < 0.15$), but a trend to a moderate concentration of the sheep and goats livestock in the other years ($0.15 < HHI < 0.25$).

In case of the live weight, HHI had a smaller value than 0.15 only in the year 2010, reflecting a low concentration, but in the other years, its value was higher than 0.15, but it did not exceed 0.18, so that we may observe a trend to a moderate concentration in a few regions: South East, Centre, South Muntenia, North West and north East, while in the other areas the live weight had lower levels (West, South West and Bucuresti-Ilfov).

Gini-Struck Index reflected similar trends, its values varying between 0.4134 and 0.4169 for livestock and between 0.4132 and 0.4467 for live weight. However, GSI had value situated between 3 and 5, therefore it shows a relative concentration in a few micro regions as mentioned above (Table 3).

Table 3. Herfindahl-Hirschman and Gini-Struck Indices for sheep and goats livestock and live weight for slaughtering

	HHI		GSI	
	For Livestock	For Live weight	For Livestock	For Live weight
2009	0.1496	0.1544	0.4134	0.4201
2010	0.1567	0.1494	0.4232	0.4132
2011	0.1521	0.1529	0.4169	0.4180
2012	0.1514	0.1586	0.4160	0.4257
2013	0.1512	0.1552	0.4157	0.4212
2014	0.1509	0.1545	0.4153	0.4202
2015	0.1506	0.1654	0.4149	0.4348
2016	0.1505	0.1746	0.4147	0.4467
2017	0.1521	0.1646	0.4169	0.4337
2018	0.1520	0.1624	0.4168	0.4308

Source: Own calculation.

3.7. Factors stimulating concentration of sheep and goats livestock and meat production

The trend to a moderate concentration in Romania regarding sheep and goat population and meat production in the recent years has been stimulated by:

- favourable geographic position of the country, soil and climate conditions, breed structure and adaptation to the local environment, practical experience and long tradition in sheep and goat growing;
- financial aids from the Romanian Government allotted to sheep breeders for stimulating the growth of livestock;
- the new orientation in the EU Common Agricultural Policy to stimulate sheep raising providing financial support (coupled aids) from European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF) destined to offer direct payments to farmers and sustain agricultural markets (European Commission, Financing the PAC) [17].
- increased sheep meat demand on the Arab market.

3.8. Impact of the concentration in meat production on food balance

Meat production growth has a good economic impact on demand/offer ratio and food balance. As sheep meat accounts for 90% in meat output resulting from sheep and goats species in Romania, the sheep meat balance in the period 2013-

2018 reflected the high level of production, the increase of export and efficiency on the country international trade (Table 4).

Table 4. Sheep meat food balance, Romania, 2013-2018 (Tons)

	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2018/2013
Production	46,800	48,600	49,323	51,232	52,200	52,119	111.36
Import	1,381	605	974	1,189	690	1,820	131.78
Export	31,129	34,319	36,010	42,226	44,603	48,491	155.77
Offer	17,052	14,886	14,287	10,135	8,287	5,448	31.94
Export/Production	66.5	70.6	73.0	82.4	85.4	93.0	139.84
Export/Import	22.5	56.7	36.9	35.5	64.6	26.6	118.22

Source: Own calculations based on NIS, 2020.

As Romanians consume only 3 kg/year sheep meat in average, most of production is exported. In the interval 2013-2018, the quantitative export increased by 55.7% from 31,129 tons in 2013 to 48,491 tons in 2018.

The sheep meat export/production ratio increased by 39.8% from 66.5 in 2013 to 93 in the year 2018, reflecting that 93 % of sheep meat production is exported due to high demand and favourable price on the external market.

The export/import ratio is much higher than 1 in all the years reflecting that Romania is a net exporting country and has a high efficient international trade with sheep meat. However, the intensified export favoured the import of sheep meat to cover the domestic market requirements.

Conclusions

- (1). The analysis emphasized an increased number of sheep and goats as well as of meat output from these two species in the period 2009-2018, stimulated by the financial aids to enlarge the livestock and production, increase offer and availabilities for export.
- (2). In 2018, Romania had 11,715 thousand sheep and goats, of which 99% are grown in the private sector and more than 68% belong to the individual agricultural small sized holdings.
- (3). Both sheep and goats livestock and live weight for slaughtering for consumption are not equally distributed in the territory of Romania.
- (4). About 81% of sheep and goats are mainly concentrated in the Central region, South East, North West, North East and West, while the highest live weight for

slaughtering is concentrated in South East, Centre, South Muntenia, North West and North East, accounting for 81.15 of total output.

(5). The moderate concentration in sheep and goats livestock and meat production was attested by HHI values which ranged between 0.1494 and 0.1654, and the GSI values which varied between 0.4132 and 0.4467.

(6). As a consequence of meat production growth the meat export raised by 55.7% and the share of export in meat output reached 93% in 2018.

(7). Therefore, the concentration growth had a positive impact on farmers' income and the trade balance, Romania being an exporting country of sheep and goat meat.

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RESEARCH REGARDING THE PROTECTION OF WHEAT CROPS AGAINST WEEDS ON A HISTOSOL FROM BERVENI COMMUNE, SATU MARE COUNTY

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Abstract. Romania is a specific country in terms of weeding. The results show that in 2010, out of the 14 million hectares officially designated for agriculture, the amount of biomass provided by weeds is about 1.21 times higher than the useful biomass. In the last thirty years there have been very few experiments in the country on weed control on different types of soil. The researches in Romania has shown that herbicide treatments should be done depending on soil type, clay content, humus and pH of the soil. Integrated Weed Management (IWM) is a complex notion that means the management of monitoring, knowing and mastering the relationships between weeds and crops through a variety of methods, including the balanced use of herbicides. The new concepts do not involve the elimination of herbicides but their use after the depletion of all alternative variants. This research aims to determine the herbicides or combinations of herbicides in rates with the best efficacy depending on each type of soil. The present paper presents the efficiency of herbicide treatments on wheat yield on a histosol from Bervenii, Satu Mare county and implicitly the control strategies. Satu Mare county has an area of 4,418 km² (1.9% of the national territory), agricultural land being 72% of this area.

Keywords: soil, weeds, wheat, herbicides, yield

1. Introduction

Despite all the progress made in agriculture in the last century, weeds are still present in cultivated lands. The technical and financial effort to reduce weed infestation is high, but it is justified through the higher level of yield and its quality. In the moment when the costs exceed the difference value of the obtained yield, weed control is no longer profitable.

The floristic composition of weeds has changed due to human intervention through the soil tillage, applied crop rotation, fertilization and herbicide treatments. Once entered the process of agricultural yield at the action of natural

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conditions is added the influence of man which is continuously accentuated, becoming at some point decisive on the weeding degree and floristic composition.

Numerous researches carried out in other countries and in our country have led to the conclusion that the fight against weeds cannot be achieved through single measures as it was considered at one time. Chemical weed control has been a major step forward and is still an effective, but not an exclusive measure. The most effective weapon is the application of a set of measures, including agro-phytotechnical ones, which include crop rotation with an important role. Soil fertility influences the infestation degree, the floristic composition of weeds and the potential yield of crops [4, 7].

The efficacy of weeds control in the field, requires a good knowledge of the pedoclimatic conditions that influence the efficiency of herbicide treatments applied preemergently or postemergently due to the different floristic composition depending on these conditions [2, 8, 9].

In order to achieve the desideratum, the researches were oriented towards the approach of some weed control strategies depending on the type of soil and the floristic composition of the weeds in the wheat crops [1,3].

The biological material used

In a modern agriculture, in the integrated management of weeds, using the chemical method of control remains a link of great importance contributing to the increase of yields by reducing the competition of weeds. Wheat, in the structure of field holds the share in Romania.

The diversity of weed species and also the differentiation in terms of their capacity have led to the further study of new and more efficient herbicides.

In fact, worldwide, an important goal of research in the field of herbicides has been the creation of new substances, more efficient herbicides, with a low impact on the environment, using very low rates per hectare, which gives them easy handling [10, 11].

Chemical control of wheat weeds is a matter of national interest, due to the damage caused to Romanian agriculture. In the last years, a series of herbicides have entered to the Romanian pesticide market with very good results in control of weeds from wheat crops [5, 6].

The experiments were located on a histosol from Bervenii, Satu-Mare county and aim to establish the influence of soil type on the floristic composition of weeds in wheat crops and the influence of weed on yield and quality of the yield. The objective was to find the best strategy for weed control from an economic point of view. This research was conducted over three years (2015, 2016, 2017).

The biological material used in this research was Glosa wheat variety.

The Glosa wheat variety was obtained at INCDA Fundulea. It is an early variety, has good resistance to fallen, is resistant to wintering, drought and heat. It also has a good resistance to ear sprouting, having medium resistance to brown rust, while it has good resistance to powdery mildew.

The dominant weed species existing in the wheat crop on the Berveni histosol are presented in (Table 1 and Figure 1)

Table 1. The dominant weed species existing in the wheat crop on the Berveni histosol

<i>Scientific name</i>	<i>Popular name</i>	<i>Density pl/sm</i>
<i>Papaver rhoeas</i>	Mac roșu	72
<i>Adonis aestivalis</i>	Cocoșei de câmp	2
<i>Viola arvensis</i>	Trei frați pătați	2
<i>Convolvulus arvensis</i>	Volbură, Rochița rândunicii	1
TOTAL		77

Fig. 1. Untreated wheat crop with herbicides on the histosol from Berveni (Original)

The herbicides applied to the autumn wheat crop are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Herbicides applied to autumn wheat crop on the histosol from Livada and Berveni

No Var.	Herbicide	Rates l, kg/ha	Active substance
1	Rival 75GD	0.015	Clorsulfuron 75%
2	Rival+Hudson	0.010+1.0	Clorsulfuron 75% + fluoxipir 200g/l
3	Dicopur D	1.0	Acid 2.4 D of dimetilamine salt 600g/l
4	Rival Star 75GD	0.015	Tribenuron-metil 75%
5	Rival Star 75GD	0.020	Tribenuron-metil 75%
6	Axial One	1.0	Pinoxaden 45g/l+florasulam 5g/l+safener
7	Axial One	2.0	Pinoxaden 45g/l+florasulam 5g/l+safener
8	Lancelot Super	0.033	Aminopiraliid 30% + florasulam 15%
9	Pallas 75 WG+Adjuvant	0.110+0.5	Piroxsulam 7.5% + safener
10	Attribut	0.060	Propoxicarbazon-sodiu 700g/kg
11	Floramix+Adjuvant	0.120+0.6	Piroxsulam70.8g/kg+florasulam14.2g/kg+ safener
12	Floramix+Adjuvant	0.260+0.6	Piroxsulam70.8g/kg+florasulam14.2g/kg+ safener
13	Rival Super Star	0.020	Tribenuron-metil 37.5% + clorsulfuron 37.5%
14	Pelican Delta	0.100	Metsulfuron 6g/kg +diflufenican 600g/kg
15	Pallas 75 WG+ Adjuvant	0.250+0.5	Piroxsulam 7.5% + safener
16	Sekator Progres OD	0.15	Iodosulfuron metil25g/l+amidosulfuron100g/l+safener
17	Dicopur Top 464 SL	1.0	Acid 2.4 D of DMA salt 344g/l+dicamba 120g/l
18	Untreated	-	-

High competition between weeds and wheat plants have a big influence on wheat yield. The highest yield and gain was registered by the variants V2, V4 and V7 (Table 3).

Table 4 shows the value of yield gain and herbicide costs compared to untreated variant in wheat crop, during 2015-2017. The highest profit was recorded by the variants V2, V4 and V10.

Table 5 shows the efficacy of herbicide treatments in wheat crop on histosol from Berveni, years average 2015-2017. The highest efficacy was noticed in case of the variants: V2, V4, V7 and V10.

The infestation degree on the histosol is high, being determined by the higher number of specimens of *Papaver rhoaes* and *Adonis aestivalis*.

Table 3. The influence of herbicide treatments on wheat crop yield from the histosol during 2015-2017

<i>No.Var.</i>	<i>Yield q/ha</i>	<i>Difference +/- against untreated variant</i>
1	81.36	28.03
2	92.50	39.17
3	79.96	26.63
4	90.43	37.10
5	85.26	31.93
6	84.03	30.70
7	88.43	35.10
8	83.40	30.07
9	85.53	32.20
10	88.20	34.87
11	86.33	33.00
12	81.40	28.07
13	82.73	29.40
14	83.76	30.43
15	79.06	25.73
16	81.76	28.43
17	80.30	26.97
18	53.33	-

Table 4. The value of yield gain and herbicides costs compared with untreated variant in wheat crop during 2015-2017

<i>No. Var.</i>	<i>Costs with herbicides Ron/ha</i>	<i>Histosol</i>	
		<i>Value of yield gain Ron/ha</i>	<i>Profit/Loss Ron/ha</i>
1	33.75	1,401.50	1,367.75
2	112.50	1,958.50	1,846.00
3	28.00	1,331.50	1,303.50
4	31.50	1,855.00	1,823.50
5	42.00	1,596.50	1,554.50
6	258.20	1,535.00	1,276.80
7	516.40	1,755.00	1,238.60
8	57.00	1,503.50	1,446.50
9	122.46	1,610.00	1,487.54
10	107.40	1,743.50	1,636.10
11	146.66	1,650.00	1,503.34
12	308.39	1,403.50	1,095.11
13	43.00	1,470.00	1,427.00
14	64.85	1,521.50	1,456.65
15	268.06	1,286.50	1,018.44
16	72.15	1,421.50	1,349.35
17	53.00	1,348.50	1,295.50
18	-	-	-

*Value of yield gain was calculated at 0.50 Ron/kg

Table 5. The efficiency of herbicide treatments on wheat crops on the Berveni histosol during 2015-2017

<i>No. Var.</i>	<i>Herbicides</i>	<i>Rate l, kg/ha</i>	<i>Application time</i>	<i>Selectivity Note EWRS</i>	<i>Efficacy %</i>
1	Rival 75GD	0.015	Post	1	84
2	Rival 75GD +Hudson	0.010+1.0	Post	1	91
3	Dicopur D	1.0	Post	1	80
4	Rival Star 75GD	0.015	Post	1	91
5	Rival Star 75GD	0.020	Post	1	86
6	Axial One	1.0	Post	1	84
7	Axial One	2.0	Post	1	87
8	Lancelot Super	0.033	Post	1	83
9	Pallas 75 WG+Adj.	0.110+0.5	Post	1	83
10	Attribut	0.060	Post	1	87
11	Floramix+Adjuvant	0.120+0.6	Post	1	85
12	Floramix+Adjuvant	0.260+0.6	Post	1	82
13	Rival Super Star	0.020	Post	1	83
14	Pelican Delta	0.100	Post	1	85
15	Pallas 75 WG+ Adj	0.250+0.5	Post	1	80
16	Sekator Progres OD	0.15	Post	1	84
17	Dicopur Top 464 SL	1.0	Post	1	75
18	Untreated	-	-	-	28

Conclusions

(1). These researches aimed to establish the technical and economic efficiency of herbicide treatments for wheat crop on the histosol from Berveni, Satu-Mare county, in the current climatic conditions and applied technologies.

(2). The researches were carried out in 2015, 2016, 2017 on a histosol with a pH of 5.1, the organic matter content was 86% being a soil rich in nutrients, the crop plant being wheat, the experiments were placed according to the rectangular Latin method, 18 variants in three repetitions, the surface of the plot being 21 sm.

(3). The highest yields were obtained in variant 2 (92.50 q / ha, the difference being 39.17 compared to untreated variant; variant 4 (90.43 q / ha, the difference being 37.10 compared to untreated variant) and in variant 7 (88.43 q / ha, the difference being 35.19).

(4). Analyzing the profit on histosol resulted that the most profitable variants were the variants (2,4,10) treated with Rival 75 GD 10g / ha + Hudson 11 / ha, Rival Star 75 GD 15g / ha followed by the variant treated with Attribute 60g / Ha.

(5). Regarding the efficacy of herbicide treatments on histosol it was established that the best weed control was registered in the variants treated with Rival 10g / ha + Hudson 1l / ha, Rival Star 75 GD 15g / ha and Axial One 2l / ha.

(6). The results obtained provide farmers and not only, information regarding the influence of soil type on the floristic composition of weeds and the infestation degree in wheat crops.

(7). Based on these results, farmers have the opportunity to establish the most effective and efficient methods of weed control in winter wheat crop.

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